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Evaluation de l'état écologique des masses d'eau de transition dans le cadre de la DCE

Assessing the ecological status of transitional water bodies under the WFD

Étude de la pertinence des peuplements du microphytobenthos estuarien pour la mise en place d'un bio-indicateur de la qualité des eaux de transition

Study on the suitability of using estuarine microphytobenthos as a bio-indicator of water quality in transitional waters

Diatom atlas of the intertidal mudflats of the Loire estuary

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- TITLE

Diatom atlas of the intertidal mudflats of the Loire estuary

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- Abstract

In order to establish the ecological status of water bodies, the European Water Framework Directive (WFD) is based on the evaluation of a number of biological quality elements, as well as physical parameters supporting the biology. In estuaries, phytoplankton monitoring was not considered relevant because of the high turbidity characterizing the large metropolitan estuaries and the French overseas departments (Guyana). This work is part of a study titled “*Évaluation de l’état écologique des masses d’eau de transition dans le cadre de la DCE - Étude de la pertinence du suivi des peuplements du microphytobenthos estuarien*” and funded by the *Agence Française pour la Biodiversité* (AFB), that is currently ongoing, and is considering the possibility of using the microphytobenthos (MPB) as a biological indicator of the ecological status of estuaries and other transitional waters.

Microphytobenthos assemblages are usually dominated by diatoms in temperate estuarine intertidal areas. In this iconographic atlas, the diatoms found in 29 samples from 3 intertidal mudflats of the Loire estuary and collected during two field campaigns (Spring and Autumn 2016) are illustrated and identified. The atlas has 602 LM photographs of 359 different taxa and stands as one of the most complete and detailed illustrated descriptions of these communities in French estuaries. Of the 359 taxa, 285 were identified to the species level, whilst 74 were identified to the genus level. The main aims of the atlas are to become a reference work for the Loire estuary, but also to become a useful identification guide for other French estuaries, given the lack of easily accessible and illustrated taxonomic works on intertidal diatoms.

For each taxon additional information is given, namely: 1) spatiotemporal distribution; 2) OMNIDIA four-letter code and *s* and *v* values for the IPS index (*Indice de Polluosensibilité Spécifique*); 3) morphometric data gathered from measurements made on 1142 valves and frustules; 4) autecological information (*i.e.* salinity preferences, habitat and growth-form). A succinct site description is provided, as well as, detailed protocols on microphytobenthos extraction and slide preparation that were specifically adapted for these sediment-dwelling diatom assemblages.

- KEY WORDS (THEMATIC AND GEOGRAPHICAL AREA)

Atlas, benthic diatoms, bio-diversity, Loire estuary, microphytobenthos, WFD

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Introduction

In order to establish the ecological status of water bodies, the European Water Framework Directive (WFD) relies on the evaluation of various biological quality elements and physicochemical parameters supporting those elements. Fishes, macroinvertebrates, phytoplankton, seagrasses and macroalgae are the biological quality elements chosen by most European countries in their monitoring programmes in transitional waters, but the reliability of the assessment methods using macroalgae and phytoplankton have been called into question (Borja and Rodriguez 2010). Despite the widespread use of several phytoplankton indicators, such as biomass, taxonomic composition and abundance, or the frequency and intensity of blooms (Brito et al. 2012), they are beset by a series of constraints and challenges (Domingues, Barbosa, and Galvão 2008; Garmendia et al. 2013) and still lack a tool that accounts for shifts in species composition and frequency of blooms in the ecological status assessment (Ferreira et al. 2011). Moreover, in very turbid estuaries, phytoplankton production is strongly limited by light or by residence time and rarely display signs of eutrophication even if the nutrient load is high (Irigoien and Castel 1997). In such systems, only a fraction of the nutrients imported by the river are used by the estuarine phytoplankton and eutrophication manifests in the coastal zone, where turbidity is lower and residence time of the water is longer (Lancelot and Muylaert 2012). Therefore, in large turbid macrotidal estuaries, such as the ones found in metropolitan France (*i.e.* Seine, Loire and Gironde), the use of phytoplankton as a monitoring tool was considered to have major deficiencies, with regard to the main Phase II Intercalibration exercise objectives of WFD-compliance (Carvalho 2012).

The extensive intertidal areas found in these estuaries provide habitat to dense populations of benthic micro-algae (usually diatoms, euglenophytes and cyanobacteria) which colonise the sediment surface layers and are collectively known as microphytobenthos (MPB). Benthic diatoms are the ubiquitous and often dominant component of these assemblages in temperate estuarine and coastal areas (Admiraal 1984; MacIntyre, Geider, and Miller 1996) and the importance of their ecological role is undeniable (Underwood 2010; Van Colen et al. 2014). Nevertheless, they are yet to be considered as a valid biological quality element in transitional waters (Poikane et al. 2014). This work is part of a study, funded by the *Agence*

Française pour la Biodiversité (AFB), that is currently ongoing, and is evaluating the applicability of using intertidal benthic diatoms as a biological indicator of the ecological status of estuaries.

In the last decades, several benthic diatom-based indices have been created and have a widespread use in assessing water quality of lotic and lentic freshwater ecosystems in Europe (e.g. Prygiel 2002; Kelly 2013). However, none of these diatom indices can be successfully applied in estuarine and coastal waters (Rovira, Trobajo, and Ibáñez 2012). A specific diatom index that incorporates the dynamic nature of these habitats (Elliott and Quintino 2007) needs to be developed but, in order to move forward, the paucity of information on the auto-ecology of marine and estuarine benthic diatoms has to be addressed beforehand (Trobajo and Sullivan 2010). This means that information on, for example, biogeography, habitat or on nutrient or salinity preferences of each benthic diatom species occurring in transitional waters still needs to be compiled in a systematic fashion. However, even for the comparatively well-studied European coasts, checklists of benthic diatoms are conspicuously rare (e.g. Hendey 1954; Hartley 1986; Snoeijs 1989). Moreover, floristic studies only represented 20% of overall MPB publications (Park et al. 2014) in the 30-year period that followed the influential review by Admiraal (1984) on the ecology of estuarine sediment-inhabiting diatoms. The reasons for this relative lack of available information are manifold. Benthic microalgae are notoriously difficult to extract from the intertidal sediments (Muylaert et al. 2002). In addition, the identification of marine benthic diatoms has always been challenging, because of the high morphological variability along environmental gradients (Cox 1986; Trobajo 2007) and a difficult taxonomy that makes species identification and inter-comparison between studies problematic (Underwood and Barnett 2006). These issues have been exacerbated by an absence of monographic works (Sullivan and Currin 2002) when compared to freshwater benthic diatoms.

The present available knowledge on benthic diatoms from traditional waters in Metropolitan France is paradigmatic of this situation. Apart from the century-old atlas “*Les Diatomées marines de France et des districts maritimes voisins*” (1897-1908), there is no recent equivalent to the very well-illustrated atlas of the phytoplanktonic diatoms of the French coasts (Gerard 1992; Paulmier 1997) and the easily accessible atlases of freshwater benthic diatoms of the Loire river basin (Ector et al. 2015), or of the Rhône-Alpes (Bey and Ector

2013) or Burgundian regions (Peeters and Ector 2017-2018). It is also still lacking an updated and comprehensive checklist of the benthic diatom species reported for French coasts and estuaries.

The main aim of the current work is to provide a readily available illustrated atlas of the diatoms found in the intertidal sediments of the Loire estuary, complemented with a species check-list that provides morphometric data and autecological information (i.e. salinity preferences, habitat and growth-form) for each taxon.

Study area and site description

The Loire estuary (Figure 1), located on the French Atlantic coast (47°17'34.42"N, 2°4'21.28"O), is the longest river in France (1012 km), with a drainage basin of 118000 km², covering about one fifth of the French territory. It is a macrotidal estuary with tidal range of ~5.4 m at Saint-Nazaire during spring tides. The flow rate ranges from 80 to 5500 m³s⁻¹ with an average of 800 m³.s⁻¹. The freshwater residence time in the estuary varies from 3 to 30 days depending on whether the river is respectively in flood or low water (Guillaud et al. 2008). Solid load input in the estuary is about 109 kg year⁻¹ (Figueres et al. 1985). It is characterized by a turbidity maximum zone with high concentrations of suspended particles from both terrestrial and marine origins (Migniot 1993) extending over 20 km on average. Long-term trends in nutrients and chlorophyll *a* in the water column can be found in Ratmaya et al. (2019). The Loire Estuary is divided into three haline domains: the polyhaline domain with salinity ranging from 18 to 30 PSU, which extends from the mouth of the estuary, the mesohaline domain, with salinity of 18 to 5, and the oligohaline domain, with salinity less than 5, upstream from the electric power plant of Cordemais.

Figure 1. The Loire estuary. The haline domains are delimited by the dashed lines

The spatial-temporal analysis of microphytobenthos diversity was carried out in three sites (Figure 2) on the polyhaline domain of the estuary, which has about 1000 ha of intertidal areas, during spring and early autumn 2016. The three sites were selected because of the existence of an identified point source of anthropogenic pressure (e.g. industrial discharge or watershed outflows) and the two sampling dates aimed at integrating the seasonal effects. For each of these sites, 5 stations were positioned along a gradient of an assumed decreasing anthropogenic pressure, the station "1" being close to the source of pressure and the "5" being the furthest away. The GPS coordinates are given in Table 1. The bathymetry of all stations was between +4 and +3 m above chart datum, corresponding to the middle tidal height of the mudflats. Remote sensing images showed that MPB biofilms were concentrated at this bathymetric level (Benyoucef et al. 2014).

Table 1. GPS coordinates of the sampling stations.

Station	Longitude	Latitude	Station	Longitude	Latitude	Station	Longitude	Latitude
DONGES 1	-2,05917	47,30840	MEAN 1	-2,181927	47,300698	BRILLANTES 1	-2,062658	47,280205
DONGES 2	-2,05919	47,30809	MEAN 2	-2,181225	47,297544	BRILLANTES 2	-2,062428	47,280761
DONGES 3	-2,05892	47,30766	MEAN 3	-2,179367	47,295735	BRILLANTES 3	-2,062159	47,281975
DONGES 4	-2,05879	47,30731	MEAN 4	-2,178191	47,292037	BRILLANTES 4	-2,062247	47,283718
DONGES 5	-2,05860	47,30702	MEAN 5	-2,178275	47,288351	BRILLANTES 5	-2,063284	47,28511

In each station, several biotic and abiotic descriptors were measured and collected (Table 2). All stations had similar sediment texture, with a mud fraction (*i.e.* < 63 μm grain size) of 85% on average. These and other results on the biotic and abiotic descriptors are available in the project progress and final reports (Buchet et al. 2015; Hernandez-Fariñas et al. 2016; Ribeiro et al. 2018) that can be downloaded at <https://professionnels.afbiodiversite.fr/fr/node/277>.

Table 2. Biotic and abiotic descriptors collected in each station

Biotic descriptors	Pore-water chemistry	Sediment physical parameters
MPB microalgal groups	Nutrients (NH_4^+ , NO_3^- , NO_2^- , SiO_2 , PO_4^{3-})	Ash-free dry weight
Diatom assemblages	Heavy metals (Hg, Al, As, Ca, Cr, Cu, Ni, Pb, Zn)	Water content
Macrofauna	PAHs (Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons)	Sediment texture
Meiofauna	Salinity	Temperature
Biomass (Chl. <i>a</i>)		

Figure 2. The polyhaline section of the Loire estuary. Méan site is near Saint-Nazaire, at the mouth of the estuary, whilst DONGES and Brillantes sites face each other 8 km upstream.

Site of DONGES

This site is in the immediate vicinity of the TOTAL refinery in DONGES, the sampling stations were all located in the 250 m long tidal creek and at a growing distance from a storm drain discharging from this SEVESO industrial facility (see Figures 3, 4 and Table 1).

Figure 3. Map of the DONGES site and location of the sampling stations.

Figure 4. View of the Donges tidal creek, near station 1. The TOTAL refinery is visible on the right.

Site of Méan (near Saint-Nazaire)

The site of Méan is a mudflat enclosed in an industrial zone and located at the mouth of the river Brivet, near the town and harbour of Saint Nazaire (figures 5, 6 and Table 1). The five stations were spread along 1.5 km, in right margin of the Brivet.

Figure 5. Map of the Méan site and location of the sampling stations.

Figure 6. View from station 5 in the Méan mudflat and facing the Loire river.

Site of Brillantes (near Le Corsept)

Brillantes is a large mud flat of several hundred hectares located on the left bank of the Loire (Figure 1). The sampling site was near the commune of Corsept, where a small tidal creek drains into the Brillantes mudflat (Figures 7, 8 and Table 1).

Figure 7. Map of the Brillantes site and location of the sampling stations.

Figure 8. View of Brillantes tidal creek station 1 (left) and of the mudflat station 5 (right). In the latter, the Donges refinery can be seen in the background, on the right bank of the Loire river.

Microphytobenthos sampling and diatom analysis: Protocols

Diatoms dominate the microphytobenthic assemblages that colonise intertidal sediments in temperate estuaries. In order to study them, they need to be separated from the sediment samples in a fashion that allows the preparation of permanent slides that are clean enough for an acceptable observation in a light microscope.

The surface sediment was collected using the contact core method (Figure 9, Ford & Honeywill, 2002). This device consists of an aluminium disk, with 5 cm in diameter, fitted with a rim of the same material that allows to collect a frozen sediment core of the top 2 millimetres of sediment, where the majority of microalgae are present, when liquid nitrogen is poured onto the aluminium disk that was previously and carefully placed on the sediment surface. The frozen samples were then stored in the laboratory, at - 80°C, for later processing.

Figure 9. The contact-core sampling method (Ford & Honeywill, 2002).

The MPB assemblages were extracted from the sampled sediment thanks to an isopycnic separation technique which uses the silica sol Ludox[®] (HS-40). This method is adapted from Ribeiro (2010) and separates the organic material from mineral particles and, thus, is able to

remove both migratory and non-migratory fractions of the diatom assemblages, as well as cyanobacteria, euglenids and other microphytobenthic algal groups. The detailed protocol is given in Annexe 1.

The MPB extracts (Figure 10, left) were initially used to determine the relative abundances of the different MPB algal groups (i.e. diatoms, cyanobacteria, euglenids, etc.) and later for diatom enumeration and taxonomic identification. For each sample, the diatom analysis was based on the preparation of two types of slides: one made from incinerated extract material (Figure 10, middle) and another one made from oxidized material (Figure 10, right). This allowed the observation of fragile and barely silicified diatoms (e.g. *Cylindrotheca closterium*, *C. gracilis* and several *Nitzschia* species) which are known to be quite abundant in mudflat assemblages. These species are frequently destroyed when a traditional oxidation cleaning method (e.g. Hydrogen peroxide) is used and are necessarily underestimated during cell counts. The detailed protocols of the two diatom cleaning methods as well as the one used for the cell counts are given below.

Figure 10. Micrographs of the same sediment sample in different stages of the diatom analysis . Left: MPB pellet after the Ludox extraction; nearly all diatom cells are in good condition and most of the silts and argyles have been removed (x400 magnification). Middle: Incinerated slide; the fragile frustules retain their overall shape, but the slide is not sufficiently clean, and the observation of the minute details in the small frustules is hindered by the incinerated material (x1000 magnification). Right: the slide made from the extract after H₂O₂ oxidation is properly cleaned but the fragile frustules have mostly disappeared (x1000 magnification). All micrographs were taken using DIC microscopy.

Microphytobenthos extraction

The chosen method is adapted from Ribeiro (2010) and separates the organic material from mineral particles and is, thus, able to remove both migratory and non-migratory fractions of the diatom assemblages, as well as cyanobacteria, euglenids and other microphytobenthic algal groups.

Given the very different densities of the sediment's mineral and organic (i.e. biofilms and meiofauna), it is not necessary to establish a density gradient centrifugation, thus simplifying the original method by De Jonge (1979). This author estimated the recovery efficiency of his method in 83% of benthic chl *a*, although Varela (1986) disputed this by finding different distributions of cells in the several Ludox concentration layers. However, subsequent authors (Blanchard et al. 1988; Méléder 2003; Ribeiro 2010) bypassed this by using only Ludox in full concentration and/or collecting all the supernate and demonstrated that the method is not qualitatively selective in terms diatom species, sizes or shapes. Burgess (2001) proposed a preliminary step, using the vortex mixer to promote fluidization of the sediment and improve extraction efficiency, that was added to the protocol advanced by Ribeiro (2010) used here. Therefore, the extraction efficiency (i.e. the percentage of cells recovered from the sediment) is not yet well established but this method has proven not to be qualitatively selective for a wide range of sediment types. A detailed protocol is given below (and schematically described in Figure 11):

- Transfer frozen contact-core sediment sample (5.5 -10.5 g in average) to a 50 mL polyethylene conical centrifuge tubes and let it unfreeze.
- Add 30 mL to the centrifuge tube and mix the sample for 3 minutes in the vortex mixer. The first 30s at maximum speed, and then reduce to an average speed. The sediment at the bottom must become fluid (check it by turning the tubes upside down). Adjust speed accordingly to achieve a fluid melange.
- Level the weight of each pair of tubes by adding a few drops of Ludox to one of tubes in a two-dish balance scale.
- Centrifuge at 3720 x g for 15 min. Given that there is no prior sieving, such a high g force is necessary to force the settling of silts and part of the clays (i.e. particles < 63 µm). Microphytobenthos, including large heavily silicified diatoms, remain suspended given their much lower specific gravity.
- Recover the supernate. Most of the organic matter accumulates in a spot in the inner wall of the tube, near the surface, but it is advisable to recover all of the supernate.
- Dilute the supernate by distributing it in 4 new 50 mL centrifuge tubes and filling them up with distilled water. One part of supernate to five of water drops the Ludox concentration to 15 %.
- Centrifuge at 1500 g for 10 min. Organic matter will settle at the bottom of the tubes. Discard the supernate and replace it with distilled water. Mix the pellet in the water and repeat procedure (i.e. centrifugations) 4 to 5 consecutive times in order to eliminate any traces of Ludox.
- Recover the pellet after the last centrifugation. This pellet will contain the organic matter and, therefore, the microphytobenthos and it is henceforth referred as extract.
- Store the extract in one to four 1.5 mL safe-lock microcentrifuge tubes at 4 °C temperature after adding a few drops of 2.5% solution of glutaraldehyde.

Figure 11. Microphytobenthos extraction method (adapted from Ribeiro 2010).

Enumeration of benthic diatoms

Diatom cleaning methods: Intertidal benthic diatoms show a wide range of shapes and sizes, from small centric species (e.g. *Minidiscus chilensis*, ~ 5 µm in diameter) to very large pennate diatoms (e.g. *Gyrosigma balticum*, up to 500 µm in length). Some of them are heavily silicified but others are very fragile and barely silicified (e.g. *Cylindrotheca closterium* or *C. gracilis* and several *Nitzschia* species). These species are usually destroyed when the traditional oxidation cleaning methods are used. In order to avoid underestimating them, two complementary diatom cleaning methods should be used and, as a result, two permanent slides must be made for each sample. The two methods were developed by Ribeiro (2010) and are the following:

- Oxidation method:** The method chosen was essentially adapted from Batterbee (1986). It is a relative aggressive chemical procedure that cleaned thoroughly the frustules by oxidation but destroyed the *Cylindrotheca* frustules. A subsample of 750 µl of extract was oxidized with 5-7 mL of hydrogen peroxide (30 %) at 90 °C for at least 4 hours. When the reaction was over, 2 mL of hydrochloric acid (6M) were added for the elimination of carbonates. Subsequently the oxidized extract was washed 4 times with ultrapure distilled water and a few drops of ammonia, for extra clay removal. The cleaned extract (diatom valves) was deposited in previously cleaned coverglasses and, after drying in a dust-free environment, mounted in Naphrax™ (refractive index, 1.73).

- **Incineration method:** The method chosen was adapted from Méléder (2003). It is a gentler method that consumes the organic matter by incineration, leaving all frustules intact. However, it also hinders the identification of very small diatoms as it may also leave mineral material (e.g. carbonates) that may hide important fine structure details of the frustules. A 15 μl subsample of extract and 400 μl of ultrapure distilled water were placed on previously cleaned 20 mm coverglasses. The resulting water meniscus was homogenized with a Pasteur's pipette to ensure an evenly distribution of the frustules and it was left to settle and dry in a dust free environment for 24-48 hours. The coverglasses were placed in a Muffle oven during 2h at 450 °C and mounted in Naphrax. Given that it is hard to control the final concentration of diatom valves/frustules in the permanent slides, it is advisable to prepare several coverslips to dry with different concentrations. The dried coverslips can be checked under the microscope, at a 200X or 400x magnification and the ones where the diatoms are either too concentrated or too sparsely distributed can be discarded.

Permanent slides: This method applies to both “incinerated” and “oxidised” slides:

- Label and clean new slides and place them on tiles over a hotplate that is turned off. Leave out the labelled end of the slides, so they can be handled in safety
- Place 2-4 drops of Naphrax (depending on viscosity) at the centre of the slides and carefully place the coverslip over the meniscus with the dry diatom material side facing the meniscus.
- Turn on the hotplate and gently press down the coverslips with wooden toothpick.
- As the Naphrax resin starts to heat up and spread throughout all the coverslip, bubbles start to form, caused by the evaporation of toluene. Let the bubbles get out with the toothpick but do not let the resin to boil too violently.
- When the evaporation starts to diminish, turn off the plate and let the slides cool down for at least 24 hours.

Enumeration of diatom cells: Ideally, diatom identification and enumeration should be made in a light microscope equipped with phase-contrast and/or differential interference contrast (DIC) microscopy for the 40x and 100x objectives and a digital camera. Protocol:

- Mark the XY Cartesian coordinates of the coverslip margins with the Vernier scale of the microscope stage. Use these coordinates to create a random series of fields of view, using the RAND function in Excel™. The aim is to counter the inevitable “margin effect” cause by the deposition of the cleaned diatom valves when the coverslip is drying and that does not allow for a homogenous distribution of the valves.
- For a consistent enumeration to take place, a set of rules need to be observed for each field of view:
 - Score only the valves that are in valvar view and more than half of their area inside the field of view.
 - Discard valves in the connective view, with the exception of the ones that can be identified to the species level.

- On the occasion an intact frustule is found, two valves are to be scored; if two valves of the same species are only half-placed in the field of view, one valve is scored.
- Broken valves are only scored if they include one of the apices and the central area.
- Valves that are impossible to identify (e.g. overlapped by other valves, with bubbles, etc.) are discarded.
- Enumeration continues until a minimum total score of 400 valves *and* 50 fields of view randomly placed in the coverslip are covered. The ideal concentration is 5-15 valves per field of view. If the concentration is higher (i.e. 20-30 valves) a minimum 25 fields of view should be covered and only if the analyst is experienced enough. Any concentration above this number a new permanent slide should be made.

The cell counting protocol for incinerated slides is very similar to the protocol describe above but instead of diatoms valves, intact frustules are scored. Only fragile species (e.g. *Cylindrotheca closterium*) are identified and scored separately, whilst the other diatoms are counted together, given that they will be identified in the oxidised slide. As an example, the relative percentage of *C. gracilis* and *C. closterium* could be determined first, from the counts of 300-500 frustules in the slide of the incinerated material. Secondly, 300-500 valves of all the other diatom taxa are scored in the slide of the oxidised material. The percentage abundance of each taxon is calculated in relation to the previously established relative percentage of *Cylindrotheca*. If the *Cylindrotheca* specimens account for 55 % of the total scores in the “incinerated” slide, the relative abundances of the other species were recalculated for the remaining 45 %. It was thus assumed that the distribution of all other species was equal in both types of slides of a given sample. Therefore, the final inventory for each sample combines the fragile and the oxidised diatom, with their abundances already in relative percentage.

Checklist of diatom species illustrated in the Atlas

The present checklist includes the 359 diatom species illustrated in this Atlas. The list was compiled in four different tables that give complementary information:

- Table 3: Species list. Includes the plate and figures numbers, the OMNIDIA codes and the IPS sensitivity class (*s*) and indicator values (*v*) for all the taxa.
- Table 4: Morphometric data. Includes the morphometric information (i.e. length, width, striae density) that resulted from biometric measurement on more than 1100 valves and frustules
- Table 5: Ecological preferences. Salinity preferences, habitat and growth-form are given for each taxon, as well as the references used in to infer them.
- Table 6: Occurrences. Species presence/absence table for the 2 seasons and the 3 sampling sites.

All micrographs were taken with a LEICA ICC50W 5-megapixel camera mounted on a Leica DM2500 LED microscope, equipped with a Brightfield and Differential Interference Contrast (DIC) and using a Leica HC PL Fluotar 100x oil objective (numerical aperture 1.32). The magnification of the micrographs in the atlas is x2000, unless otherwise indicated. This allows a more direct comparison between taxa of different sizes. This magnification means that, in the plates, 1 cm corresponds to 5 μm of actual object size.

The identification of diatoms was carried out according to the following works: Peragallo and Peragallo (1897-1908), Hendey (1964); Germain (1981), Krammer and Lange-Bertalot (1986, 1988, 1991a, 1991b), Round et al. (1990), Snoeijs (1993), Snoeijs and Vilbaste (1994), Snoeijs and Potopova (1995), Snoeijs and Kasperoviciene (1996), Snoeijs and Balashova (1998), Hasle and Syvertsen (1997), Witkowski et al. (2000), Lange-Bertalot, 2001 (2001), Krammer and Lange-Bertalot (2002), Krammer and Lange-Bertalot, (2003); Levkov (2009), Ector et al. (2015), Lange-Bertalot et al (2017), as well as, the doctoral theses by Kuylenstierna (1989-1990), Rincé (1993), Sabbe (1997) and Ribeiro (2010).

The arrangement and placement of the different taxa in the 42 plates of this atlas follow when possible the classification system proposed by Round et al. (1990). Even though it is outdated, it is a conventional and familiar classification to anyone that has worked with diatoms.

Table 3: List of the 359 diatom species illustrated in this Atlas. IPS index sensitivity class (s) and indicator values (v) available in the OMNIDIA database are also given (n.a. indicates when they were not available). Taxa not identified to the species level were given the OMNIDIA genus code.

Species	Figures	Codes OMNIDIA	IPS (s)	Sensitivity class	IPS (v)	Indicator value
<i>Achnanthydium cf. druartii</i> Rimet & Couté	Pl. 18; Fig. 20-21	ADRU	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Achnanthydium exiguum</i> (Grunow) Czarnecki	Pl. 18; Fig. 22-23	ADEG	3	somewhat tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Achnanthydium cf. saprophilum</i> (H. Kobayashi & Mayama) Round & Bukhtiyarova	Pl. 18; Fig. 18-19	ADSA	3	somewhat tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Achnanthydium cf. subhudsonis</i> (Hustedt) H. Kobayasi	Pl. 18; Fig. 16-17	ADSH	5	very sensitive	2	Medium indication value
<i>Achnanthydium</i> sp. 1	Pl. 18; Fig. 1-10	ACHD sp1	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Achnanthydium</i> sp. 2	Pl. 18; Fig. 15	ACHD sp2	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Achnanthydium</i> sp. 3	Pl. 18; Fig. 11-12	ACHD sp3	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Achnanthydium</i> sp. 4	Pl. 18; Fig. 13	ACHD sp4	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Achnanthydium</i> sp. 5	Pl. 18; Fig. 14	ACHD sp5	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Actinocyclus normanii</i> (W. Gregory ex Greville) Hustedt	Pl. 1; Fig. 1	ANMN	2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Actinocyclus octonarius</i> var. <i>tenellus</i> (Brébisson) Hendey	Pl. 1; Fig. 2	AOTE	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Actinocyclus senarius</i> (Ehrenberg) Ehrenberg	Pl. 7; Fig. 6-7	ASEN	2.8	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Adlafia</i> sp. 1	Pl. 25; Fig. 13	ADSP sp1	2	n.a.	1	n.a.
<i>Amphora cf. copulata</i> (Kützing) Schoeman & Archibald (sensu Sabbe 1997)	Pl. 36; Fig. 1-3	ACOP	4	sensitive	2	Medium indication value
<i>Amphora cf. helenensis</i> Giffen	Pl. 36; Fig. 4	AHLN	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Amphora cf. indistincta</i> Levkov	Pl. 36; Fig. 5-7	AMID	5	very sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Amphora ovalis</i> (Kützing) Kützing	Pl. 36; Fig. 14	AOVA	3	somewhat tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Amphora aff. pediculus</i> (Kützing) Grunow	Pl. 36; Fig. 8	APED	4	sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Amphora pediculus</i> (Kützing) Grunow	Pl. 36; Fig. 9	APED	4	sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Amphora cf. subacutiuscula</i> Schoeman	Pl. 36; Fig. 10-13	ASAC	2.8	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Amphora cf. vetula</i> Levkov	Pl. 36; Fig. 15-17	AVTU	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Anomoeoneis sphaerophora</i> Pfitzer	Pl. 20; Fig. 16	ASPH	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Anorthoneis cf. tenuis</i> Hustedt	Pl. 17; Fig. 11	ANTN	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Asterionella formosa</i> Hassall	Pl. 14; Fig. 6	AFOR	4	sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Asteromphalus flabellatus</i> (Brébisson) Greville	Pl. 3; Fig. 6	ASFL nw	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Aulacoseira ambigua</i> (Grunow) Simonsen	Pl. 11; Fig. 1-2	AAMB	3	somewhat tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Aulacoseira brasiliensis</i> P.I. Tremarin, L. Carvalho Torgan & T.A. Veiga Ludwig	Pl. 11; Fig. 3-5	AUBR	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Aulacoseira granulata</i> (Ehrenberg) Simonsen	Pl. 11; Fig. 13-14	AUGR	2.9	tolerant	1	Low indication value

Species	Figures	Codes OMNIDIA	IPS (s)	Sensitivity class	IPS (v)	Indicator value
<i>Aulacoseira islandica</i> (O. Müller) Simonsen	Pl. 11; Fig. 10-12	AUIS	5	very sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Aulacoseira pusilla</i> (F. Meister) A. Tuji & A. Houk	Pl. 11; Fig. 6-9	AUPU	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Aulacoseira subartica</i> (O. Müller) Haworth	Pl. 11; Fig. 15-17	AUSU	4	sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Bacillaria paxillifera</i> (O. F. Müller) T. Marsson	Pl. 33; Fig. 5	BPAX	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Belonastrium berolinense</i> (Lemmermann) Round & Maidana	Pl. 13; Fig. 35-36	BBER	3	somewhat tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Berkeleya fennica</i> Juhlin-Dannfelt	Pl. 20; Fig. 8	BFEN	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Biremis lucens</i> (Hustedt) K. Sabbe, A. Witkowski & W. Vyverman	Pl. 20; Fig. 15	BLUC	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Brockmanniella brockmannii</i> (Hustedt) Hasle, Stosch & Swertsen	Pl. 12; Fig. 5	BBRO	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Caloneis aemula</i> (A. Schmidt) Cleve	Pl. 19; Fig. 4	CAEM	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Caloneis schumanniana</i> (Grunow) Cleve	Pl. 19; Fig. 5	CSHU	5	very sensitive	3	High indication value
<i>Caloneis westii</i> (W. Smith) Hendey	Pl. 19; Fig. 6	CWES	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Catenula adhaerens</i> (Mereschkowsky) Mereschkowsky	Pl. 36; Fig. 25	CADH	2	tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Cavinula cf. lapidosa</i> (Krasske) Lange-Bertalot	Pl. 20; Fig. 9	CVLP	5	very sensitive	2	Medium indication value
<i>Ceratallus smithii</i> Ralfs	Pl. 11; Fig. 21	CRSM	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Chaetoceros</i> spp. [Hypnospores]	Pl. 9; Fig. 7-13	CHAE	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Climaconeis fasciculata</i> (Grunow ex Cleve) E. J. Cox	Pl. 21; Fig. 1	CLFA	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Cocconeis disculus</i> (Schumann) Cleve	Pl. 17; Fig. 15	CDIS	5	very sensitive	2	Medium indication value
<i>Cocconeis lineata</i> Ehrenberg	Pl. 17; Fig. 18-21	CLNT	4	sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Cocconeis cf. neathumensis</i> Krammer	Pl. 17; Fig. 13-14	CNTH	3	somewhat tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Cocconeis pediculus</i> Ehrenberg	Pl. 17; Fig. 23-25	CPED	4	sensitive	2	Medium indication value
<i>Cocconeis placentula</i> var. <i>euglypta</i> (Ehrenberg) Grunow	Pl. 17; Fig. 22	CPLE	3.6	somewhat tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Cocconeis scutellum</i> Ehrenberg	Pl. 17; Fig. 17	CSCU	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Cocconeis stauroneiformis</i> H. Okuno	Pl. 17; Fig. 16	CSTF	2.8	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Cocconeis</i> sp. 1	Pl. 17; Fig. 12	COCO sp1	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Coccinodiscus jonesianus</i> (Greville) Ostenfeld	Pl. 2; Fig. 3-4	CICO	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Craticula subminuscula</i> (Manguin) C. E. Wetzel & Ector	Pl. 25; Fig. 10-11	CSNU	2	tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Ctenophora pulchella</i> var. <i>lanceolata</i> (O'Meara) L. Bukhtiyarova	Pl. 14; Fig. 1-2	CTPL	3	somewhat tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Cyclostephanos invisitatus</i> (M. H. Hohn & Hellermann) E. C. Theriot, Stoermer & Håkasson	Pl. 6; Fig. 24-26	CINV	2.6	tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Cyclotella cf. atomus</i> var. <i>gracilis</i> Genkal & Kiss	Pl. 6; Fig. 8-9	CAGR	3	somewhat tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Cyclotella cf. choctawhatcheeana</i> Prasad	Pl. 6; Fig. 3-4	CCHO	2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Cyclotella cf. meduanae</i> H. Germain	Pl. 6; Fig. 5-6	CMED	2	tolerant	1	Low indication value

Species	Figures	Codes OMNIDIA	IPS (s)	Sensitivity class	IPS (v)	Indicator value
<i>Cyclotella meneghiniana</i> Kützing	Pl. 6; Fig. 2	CMEN	2	tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Cyclotella</i> sp. 1	Pl. 6; Fig. 1	CYCL sp1	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Cyclotella</i> sp. 2	Pl. 6; Fig. 7	CYCL sp2	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Cylindrotheca closterium</i> (Ehrenberg) Reimann & J.C.Lewin	Pl. 34; Fig. 5	CCLO	1	very tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Cylindrotheca gracilis</i> (Brébisson ex Kützing) Grunow	Pl. 34; Fig. 6-7	CYGR	1.8	very tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Cymatopleura elliptica</i> (Brébisson) W.Smith	Pl. 42; Fig. 1-3	CELL	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Cymatopleura solea</i> (Brébisson) W.Smith	Pl. 42; Fig. 4	CSOL	4	sensitive	2	Medium indication value
<i>Cymatosira belgica</i> Grunow	Pl. 12; Fig. 6	CBEL	2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Cymbella tumida</i> (Brébisson) Van Heurck	Pl. 16; Fig. 5	CTUM	3	somewhat tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Cymbella</i> sp. 1	Pl. 16; Fig. 4	CYMB sp1	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Cymbella</i> sp. 2	Pl. 16; Fig. 3	CYMB sp2	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Cymbopleura</i> cf. <i>amphicephala</i> (Nägeli) Krammer	Pl. 16; Fig. 2	CBAM	4	sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Delphineis minutissima</i> (Hustedt) Simonsen	Pl. 15; Fig. 6-8	DELM	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Delphineis surirelloides</i> (Simonsen) G.W.Andrews	Pl. 15; Fig. 9	DSRL	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Denticula subtilis</i> Grunow	Pl. 31; Fig. 11-12	DSUB	2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Diadesmis confervacea</i> Kützing	Pl. 20; Fig. 13	DCOF	1	very tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Diploneis aestuarii</i> Hustedt	Pl. 20; Fig. 1	DAES	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Diploneis schmidtii</i> Cleve	Pl. 20; Fig. 1	DSMI	5	very sensitive	3	High indication value
<i>Diploneis</i> cf. <i>vacillans</i> (A.Schmidt) Cleve	Pl. 20; Fig. 3	DVAC	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Diploneis vetula</i> (A.Schmidt) Cleve	Pl. 18; Fig. 45	DVET	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Diploneis weissflagii</i> (A.Schmidt) Cleve	Pl. 19; Fig. 7-8	DWEI	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Diploneis</i> sp. 1	Pl. 20; Fig. 4	DIPL sp1	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Discostella pseudostelligera</i> (Hustedt) Houk & Klee	Pl. 6; Fig. 13-15	DPST	4	sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Discostella stelligera</i> var. <i>tenuis</i> (Hustedt) Houk & Klee	Pl. 6; Fig. 10-11	DSTT	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Discostella</i> cf. <i>waltereckii</i> (Hustedt) Houk & Klee	Pl. 6; Fig. 12	DWOL	4	sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Encyonema</i> sp. 1	Pl. 16; Fig. 1	ENCY sp1	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Entomoneis alata</i> (Ehrenberg) Ehrenberg	Pl. 37; Fig. 1-3	EALA	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Entomoneis paludosa</i> (W.Smith) Reimer	Pl. 37; Fig. 4	EPAL	2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Eolimna</i> sp. 1	Pl. 25; Fig. 12	EOLI sp1	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Epithemia adnata</i> (Kützing) Brébisson	Pl. 37; Fig. 5	EADN	4	sensitive	3	High indication value
<i>Epithemia sorex</i> Kützing	Pl. 37; Fig. 6	ESOR	4	sensitive	2	Medium indication value

Species		Figures	Codes OMNIDIA	IPS (s)	Sensitivity class	IPS (v)	Indicator value
<i>Eunotia cf. minor</i> (Kützing) Grunow		Pl. 36; Fig. 24	EMIN	4.6	sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Eunotia sp. 1</i>		Pl. 36; Fig. 23	EUNO sp1	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Eunotogramma cf. dubium</i> Hustedt		Pl. 12; Fig. 12-13	EUDU	2.5	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Fallacia amphipleuroides</i> (Hustedt) D.G.Mann		Pl. 26; Fig. 7	FAMP	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Fallacia helenis</i> (Schulz) D.G.Mann		Pl. 26; Fig. 4	FHEL	5	very sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Fallacia margino-punctata</i> K.Sabbe & W.Vyverman		Pl. 26; Fig. 8	FMPU	2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Fallacia cf. ny</i> (Cleve) D.G.Mann		Pl. 26; Fig. 5	FANY	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Fallacia pygmaea</i> (Kützing) Strickle & D.G.Mann		Pl. 26; Fig. 3	FPYG	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Fallacia scaldensis</i> K.Sabbe & K.Muylaert		Pl. 26; Fig. 6	FSCl	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Fallacia cf. wuestii</i> (R.Simonsen) K.Sabbe & K.Muylaert		Pl. 26; Fig. 9	FWUE	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Fallacia sp. 1</i>		Pl. 26; Fig. 1-2	FALL sp1	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Fistulifera saprophila</i> (Lange-Bertalot & Bonik) Lange-Bertalot		Pl. 25; Fig. 17-18	FSAP	2.3	tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Fragilaria cf. improbula</i> A.Witkowski & Lange-Bertalot		Pl. 13; Fig. 1-2	FIMP	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Fragilaria cf. capucina</i> Desmazières		Pl. 13; Fig. 19-20	FCAP	4.5	sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Fragilaria tenera</i> var. <i>nanana</i> (Lange-Bertalot) Lange-Bertalot & S.Ulrich		Pl. 14; Fig. 7	FTNA	5	very sensitive	2	Medium indication value
<i>Fragilaria sensu lato</i> (s.l.) sp. 1		Pl. 13; Fig. 9	FRAG sl sp1	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Fragilaria s.l. sp. 2</i>		Pl. 13; Fig. 10-12	FRAG sl sp2	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Fragilaria s.l. sp. 3</i>		Pl. 13; Fig. 13-14	FRAG sl sp3	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Fragilaria s.l. sp. 4</i>		Pl. 13; Fig. 15-17	FRAG sl sp4	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Fragilaria s.l. sp. 5</i>		Pl. 13; Fig. 18	FRAG sl sp5	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Frustulia interposita</i> (Lewis) De Toni		Pl. 20; Fig. 12	FITP	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Gedaniella flavovirens</i> (H.Takano) C.Li, A.Witkowski & M.P.Ashworth		Pl. 13; Fig. 3-4	GEDF nw	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Geissleria decussis</i> (Østrup) Lange-Bertalot & Metzeltin		Pl. 25; Fig. 9	GDEC	4.8	sensitive	2	Medium indication value
<i>Gomphonema sp. 1</i>		Pl. 17; Fig. 5-6	GOMP sp1	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Gomphonema sp. 2</i>		Pl. 17; Fig. 3-4	GOMP sp2	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Gomphonema sp. 3</i>		Pl. 17; Fig. 8	GOMP sp3	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Gomphonema sp. 4</i>		Pl. 17; Fig. 7	GOMP sp4	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Gomphonema sp. 5</i>		Pl. 17; Fig. 9	GOMP sp5	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Gomphonema sp. 6</i>		Pl. 17; Fig. 1	GOMP sp6	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Gomphonema sp. 7</i>		Pl. 17; Fig. 2	GOMP sp7	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Grunowia tabellaris</i> (Grunow) Rabenhorst		Pl. 33; Fig. 15	NSIT	5	very sensitive	2	Medium indication value

Species	Figures	Codes OMNIDIA	IPS (s)	Sensitivity class	IPS (v)	Indicator value
<i>Gyrosigma acuminatum</i> var. <i>gallicum</i> (Grunow) Cleve	Pl. 27; Fig. 1-2	GVAG	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Gyrosigma attenuatum</i> (Kützing) Rabenhorst	Pl. 27; Fig. 3-4	GYAT	4	sensitive	3	High indication value
<i>Gyrosigma balticum</i> (Ehrenberg) Rabenhorst	Pl. 28; Fig. 8	GBAL	2.5	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Gyrosigma eximium</i> (Thwaites) Boyer	Pl. 28; Fig. 6-7	GYEX	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Gyrosigma fasciola</i> (Ehrenberg) J.W.Griffith & Henfrey	Pl. 28; Fig. 3-4	GFAS	2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Gyrosigma limosum</i> Sterrenburg & Underwood	Pl. 26; Fig. 25-27	GLIM	4	sensitive	3	High indication value
<i>Gyrosigma macrum</i> (W.Smith) J.W.Griffith & Henfrey	Pl. 29; Fig. 6	GYMA	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Gyrosigma scalproides</i> (Rabenhorst) Cleve	Pl. 28; Fig. 5	GSCA	2.8	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Gyrosigma wansbeckii</i> (Donkin) Cleve	Pl. 26; Fig. 28	GWAN	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Halamphora</i> cf. <i>abuensis</i> (Foged) Levkov	Pl. 36; Fig. 20-21	HLAB	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Halamphora</i> sp. 1	Pl. 36; Fig. 18	HALA sp1	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Halamphora</i> sp. 2	Pl. 36; Fig. 19	HALA sp2	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Halamphora</i> sp. 3	Pl. 36; Fig. 22	HALA sp3	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Hantzschia amphioxys</i> (Ehrenberg) Grunow	Pl. 33; Fig. 1	HAMP	1.5	very tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Haslea nipkowitzii</i> (Meister) M.Poulin & G.Massé	Pl. 28; Fig. 1-2	HNIP	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Hippodonta caotica</i> A.Witkowski, H. Lange-Bertalot & D. Metzeltin	Pl. 25; Fig. 7	HCAO	4.3	sensitive	2	Medium indication value
<i>Hippodonta hungarica</i> (Østrup) Lange-Bertalot, Metzeltin & A.Witkowski	Pl. 25; Fig. 5-6	HHUN	4	sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Hippodonta linearis</i> (Østrup) Lange-Bertalot, Metzeltin & A.Witkowski	Pl. 25; Fig. 8	HILI	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Humidophila contenta</i> (Grunow) Lowe, Kociolek, Johansen, Van de Vijver, Lange-Bertalot & Kopalová	Pl. 20; Fig. 14	HUCO	4	sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Karayevia amoena</i> (Hustedt) Bukhtiyarova	Pl. 18; Fig. 39-41	KAAM	4	sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Karayevia clevei</i> (Grunow) Round & Bukhtiyarova	Pl. 18; Fig. 42-44	KCLE	4	sensitive	2	Medium indication value
<i>Lindavia comta</i> (Kützing) Nakov, Gullory, Julius, Theriot & Alverson	Pl. 6; Fig. 27-28	LCMT	5	very sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Lithodermium undulatum</i> Ehrenberg	Pl. 12; Fig. 1-2	LUND	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Luticola frequentissima</i> Levkov, Metzeltin & A.Pavlov	Pl. 20; Fig. 5	LFRQ	2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Luticola goeppertiana</i> (Bleisch) D.G.Mann ex J.Rarick, S.Wu, S.S.Lee & Edlund	Pl. 20; Fig. 6-7	LGOE	2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Mastogloia baltica</i> Grunow	Pl. 14; Fig. 11	MBAL	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Mastogloia</i> cf. <i>danseyi</i> (Thwaites) Thwaites ex W.Smith	Pl. 14; Fig. 9-10	MDAN	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Mayamaea atomus</i> (Kützing) Lange-Bertalot	Pl. 25; Fig. 19	MAAT	2.2	tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Mayamaea</i> cf. <i>excelsa</i> (Krasske) Lange-Bertalot	Pl. 25; Fig. 15-16	MAEX	3	somewhat tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Meloneis mimallis</i> I.Louvrou, D.B.Danielidis & A.Economou-Amilli	Pl. 15; Fig. 5	MEMI	0	n.a.	0	n.a.

Species	Figures	Codes OMNIDIA	IPS (s)	Sensitivity class	IPS (v)	Indicator value
<i>Melosira lineata</i> (Dillwyn) C.Agarth	Pl. 8 ; Fig. 7-9	MLIN	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Melosira moniliformis</i> (O.F.Müller) C.Agarth	Pl. 9; Fig. 1-6	MMON	2.5	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Melosira nummuloides</i> C.Agarth	Pl. 8; Fig. 3-4	MNUM	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Melosira varians</i> C.Agarth	Pl. 8; Fig. 5-6	MVAR	4	sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Melosira</i> sp. 1	Pl. 8; Fig. 1-2	MELO sp1	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Meridion circulare</i> (Greville) C.Agarth	Pl. 14; Fig. 12	MCIR	5	very sensitive	2	Medium indication value
<i>Navicula cf. abscondita</i> Hustedt	Pl. 22; Fig. 15-16	NABS	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Navicula aleksandrae</i> Lange-Bertalot, Bogaczewicz-Adamczak & A.Witkowski	Pl. 23; Fig. 15-16	NALK	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Navicula cf. antonii</i> Lange-Bertalot	Pl. 23; Fig. 27	NANT	4	sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Navicula cf. arenaria</i> Donkin	Pl. 24; Fig. 6-7	NARE	4	sensitive	3	High indication value
<i>Navicula bipustulata</i> Mann	Pl. 22; Fig. 22-23	NBIP	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Navicula bozenae</i> Lange-Bertalot, A.Witkowski & Zgrundo	Pl. 23; Fig. 18	NBOZ	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Navicula cincta</i> (Ehrenberg) Ralfs in Pritchard	Pl. 23; Fig. 21-22	NCIN	3	somewhat tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Navicula cf. cryptotenella</i> Lange-Bertalot	Pl. 22; Fig. 8	NCTE	4	sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Navicula digitoradiata</i> (W.Gregory) Ralfs	Pl. 23; Fig. 23-26	NDIG	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Navicula dilucida</i> Hustedt	Pl. 22; Fig. 9	NDLD	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Navicula erifuga</i> Lange-Bertalot	Pl. 22; Fig. 5-7	NERI	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Navicula cf. flagellifera</i> Hustedt	Pl. 23; Fig. 1-3	NFGF	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Navicula gregaria</i> Donkin [morphotype 1]	Pl. 23; Fig. 4	NGRE m1	3.4	somewhat tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Navicula gregaria</i> Donkin [morphotype 2]	Pl. 23; Fig. 5	NGRE 2	3.4	somewhat tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Navicula lanceolata</i> (Agardh) Ehrenberg	Pl. 24; Fig. 4-5	NLAN	3.8	somewhat tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Navicula microdigitoradiata</i> Lange-Bertalot	Pl. 22; Fig. 20-21	NMDG	3	somewhat tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Navicula pargemina</i> G.J.C.Underwood & M.L.Yallop	Pl. 25; Fig. 20-23	NPGN	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Navicula cf. pargemina</i> G.J.C.Underwood & M.L.Yallop	Pl. 25; Fig. 24-25	NPGN	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Navicula peregrina</i> (Ehrenberg) Kützing	Pl. 24; Fig. 8	NPRG	2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Navicula perminuta</i> Grunow	Pl. 25; Fig. 27-29	NPNU	2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Navicula cf. perminuta</i> Grunow	Pl. 25; Fig. 30-31	NPNU	2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Navicula phyllepta</i> Kützing	Pl. 23; Fig. 9	NPHY	2.6	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Navicula cf. phyllepta</i> Kützing [morphotype 1]	Pl. 23; Fig. 13	NPHY	2.6	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Navicula cf. phyllepta</i> Kützing [morphotype 2]	Pl. 23; Fig. 10-12	NPHY	2.6	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Navicula cf. salinarum</i> Grunow	Pl. 22; Fig. 18-19	NSAL	2.6	tolerant	2	Medium indication value

Species	Figures	Codes OMNIDIA	IPS (s)	Sensitivity class	IPS (v)	Indicator value
<i>Navicula salinicola</i> Hustedt	Pl. 25; Fig. 34	NSLC	2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Navicula cf. salinicola</i> Hustedt	Pl. 25; Fig. 35-38	NSLC	2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Navicula slesvicensis</i> Grunow	Pl. 24; Fig. 3	NSLE	3	somewhat tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Navicula spartinetensis</i> Sullivan & Reimer	Pl. 22; Fig. 1-3	NXSP	2.4	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Navicula cf. starmachioides</i> A. Witkowski & Lange-Bertalot	Pl. 25; Fig. 26	NSTA	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Navicula tripunctata</i> (O.F. Müller) Bory	Pl. 24; Fig. 1-2	NTPT	4.4	sensitive	2	Medium indication value
<i>Navicula cf. utlandshoerniensis</i> Van Landingham	Pl. 23; Fig. 19-20	NUTL	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Navicula veneta</i> Kützing	Pl. 26; Fig. 7	NVEN	1	very tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Navicula viminoides</i> subsp. <i>cosmomarina</i> Lange-Bertalot, A. Witkowski, Bogaczewicz-Adamczak & Zgrundo	Pl. 23; Fig. 17	NVMC nw	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Navicula wiesneri</i> Lange-Bertalot	Pl. 22; Fig. 13-14	NWIE	3	somewhat tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 1	Pl. 22; Fig. 17	NAVI sp1	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 2	Pl. 25; Fig. 32	NAVI sp2	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 3	Pl. 25; Fig. 33	NAVI sp3	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 4	Pl. 22; Fig. 10-11	NAVI sp4	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 5	Pl. 22; Fig. 5	NAVI sp5	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 6	Pl. 22; Fig. 6	NAVI sp6	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 7	Pl. 22; Fig. 24-25	NAVI sp7	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 8	Pl. 22; Fig. 4	NAVI sp8	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 9	Pl. 23; Fig. 6	NAVI sp9	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 10	Pl. 25; Fig. 39	NAVI sp10	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 11	Pl. 25; Fig. 40	NAVI sp11	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Navicula</i> s.l. sp. 1	Pl. 23; Fig. 14	NAVI sl sp1	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Navicula</i> s.l. sp. 2	Pl. 25; Fig. 41-43	NAVI sl sp2	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Navicula</i> s.l. sp. 3	Pl. 23; Fig. 8	NAVI sl sp3	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Nitzschia acicularis</i> (Kützing) W. Smith	Pl. 33; Fig. 3	NACI	2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Nitzschia aequorea</i> Hustedt	Pl. 30; Fig. 22	NEQO	2	tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Nitzschia agnita</i> Hustedt	Pl. 30; Fig. 29	NAGN	3.2	somewhat tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Nitzschia amphibia</i> Grunow	Pl. 30; Fig. 19	NAMP	1	very tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Nitzschia angularis</i> W. Smith	Pl. 33; Fig. 4	NIAG	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Nitzschia brevissima</i> Grunow	Pl. 31; Fig. 7	NBRE	2	tolerant	3	High indication value

Species	Figures	Codes OMNIDIA	IPS (s)	Sensitivity class	IPS (v)	Indicator value
<i>Nitzschia cf. capitellata</i> Hustedt	Pl. 30; Fig. 27	NCPL	1	very tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Nitzschia cf. dissipata</i> (Kützing) Rabenhorst	Pl. 30; Fig. 30-32	NDIS	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Nitzschia cf. distans</i> W.Gregory	Pl. 30; Fig. 25-26	NIDS	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Nitzschia dubia</i> W. Smith	Pl. 31; Fig. 6	NDUB	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Nitzschia cf. dubia</i> W. Smith	Pl. 32; Fig. 1	NDUB	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Nitzschia cf. filiformis</i> (W. Smith) Van Heurck	Pl. 32; Fig. 2-3	NFIL	3	somewhat tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Nitzschia fonticola</i> (Grunow) Grunow	Pl. 30; Fig. 10-11	NFON	3.5	somewhat tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Nitzschia frustulum</i> (Kützing) Grunow in Cleve & Grunow	Pl. 30; Fig. 3-6	NIFR	2	tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Nitzschia cf. gessneri</i> Hustedt	Pl. 32; Fig. 4	NGES	3	somewhat tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Nitzschia incognita</i> Legler & Krasske	Pl. 30; Fig. 24	NICN	2.5	tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Nitzschia aff. inconspicua</i> Grunow	Pl. 30; Fig. 2	NINC	2.8	tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Nitzschia lanceola</i> var. <i>minutula</i> Grunow	Pl. 30; Fig. 18	NLMN	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Nitzschia lorenziana</i> Grunow	Pl. 31; Fig. 8	NLOR	2.5	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Nitzschia maxima</i> Grunow	Pl. 32; Fig. 5	NMAX	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Nitzschia microcephala</i> Grunow	Pl. 30; Fig. 17	NMIC	1	very tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Nitzschia nana</i> Grunow	Pl. 31; Fig. 9	NNAN	4	sensitive	2	Medium indication value
<i>Nitzschia ovalis</i> H.J.Arnott	Pl. 30; Fig. 20	NOVA	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Nitzschia palea</i> (Kützing) W. Smith	Pl. 30; Fig. 21	NPAL	1	very tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Nitzschia cf. parvula</i> W. Smith non Lewis	Pl. 31; Fig. 2	NPAR	2.8	tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Nitzschia pellucida</i> Grunow	Pl. 31; Fig. 10	NIPE	2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Nitzschia cf. pseudofonticola</i> Hustedt	Pl. 30; Fig. 28	NPSF	2.9	tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Nitzschia cf. pusilla</i> Grunow	Pl. 30; Fig. 12-13	NIPU	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Nitzschia recta</i> Hantzsch ex Rabenhorst	Pl. 34; Fig. 1	NREC	3	somewhat tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Nitzschia rhopaloides</i> Hustedt	Pl. 31; Fig. 16	NIRH	1.8	very tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Nitzschia sigma</i> (Kützing) W. Smith	Pl. 34; Fig. 2-4	NSIG	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Nitzschia supralitorea</i> Lange-Bertalot	Pl. 31; Fig. 1	NZSU	1.5	very tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Nitzschia thermaloides</i> Hustedt	Pl. 31; Fig. 3-5	NTHE	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Nitzschia tubicola</i> Grunow	Pl. 30; Fig. 7-9	NTUB	2.8	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Nitzschia</i> sp. 1	Pl. 32; Fig. 6	NITZ sp1	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Nitzschia</i> sp. 2	Pl. 30; Fig. 14	NITZ sp2	0	n.a.	0	n.a.

Species	Figures	Codes OMNIDIA	IPS (s)	Sensitivity class	IPS (v)	Indicator value
<i>Nitzschia</i> sp. 3	Pl. 30; Fig. 23	NITZ sp3	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Nitzschia</i> sp. 4	Pl. 30; Fig. 16	NITZ sp4	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Nitzschia</i> sp. 5	Pl. 30; Fig. 15	NITZ sp6	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Nitzschia</i> sp. 6	Pl. 31; Fig. 14	NITZ sp7	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Nitzschia</i> sp. 7	Pl. 33; Fig. 2	NITZ sp8	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Nitzschia</i> sp. 8	Pl. 31; Fig. 15	NITZ sp9	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Nupella</i> sp. 1	Pl. 25; Fig. 14	NUPE sp1	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Odontella rostrata</i> (Hustedt) Simonsen	Pl. 11; Fig. 18-20	OROS	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Opephora horstiana</i> A. Witkowski	Pl. 13; Fig. 8	OHOR	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Opephora mutabilis</i> (Grunow) Sabbe & Wyverman	Pl. 13; Fig. 6-7	OMUT	2.8	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Paralia</i> cf. <i>fenestrata</i> Sawai & Nagumo	Pl. 7; Fig. 1-3	PFEN	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Paralia sulcata</i> (Ehrenberg) Cleve	Pl. 7; Fig. 4-5	PSUL	2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Petrodictyon gemma</i> (Ehrenberg) D.G.Mann	Pl. 40; Fig. 2	PGEM	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Pinnularia divergentissima</i> (Grunow) Cleve	Pl. 19; Fig. 3	PDVG	5	very sensitive	2	Medium indication value
<i>Pinnularia</i> sp. 1	Pl. 19; Fig. 1	PINU sp1	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Pinnularia</i> sp. 2	Pl. 19; Fig. 2	PINU sp2	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Plagiogrammopsis crawfordii</i> A. Witkowski	Pl. 12; Fig. 7	PGGC	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Plagiogrammopsis minima</i> (Salah) Sabbe & A. Witkowski	Pl. 12; Fig. 11	PGMI	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Plagiogrammopsis vanheurckii</i> (Grunow) Hasle, Stosch & Syvertsen	Pl. 12; Fig. 8-10	PLGV	2.5	tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Plagiogrammopsis confusum</i> (Hendey) Paddock	Pl. 20; Fig. 10	PLCF nw	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Plagiotropis seriata</i> (Cleve) Kuntze	Pl. 21; Fig. 2-3	PTSR nw	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Plagiotropis</i> cf. <i>vanheurckii</i> Grunow	Pl. 21; Fig. 4-5	PVHK	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Planothidium delicatulum</i> (Kützing) Round & Bukhtiyarova	Pl. 18; Fig. 34-38	PTDE	3	somewhat tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Planothidium frequentissimum</i> (Lange-Bertalot) Lange-Bertalot	Pl. 18; Fig. 27	PLFQ	3.4	tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Planothidium hauckianum</i> (Grunow) Bukhtiyarova	Pl. 18; Fig. 31-32	PTHA	2.8	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Planothidium lanceolatum</i> (Brébisson ex Kützing) Lange-Bertalot	Pl. 18; Fig. 24-26	PTLA	4.6	sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Planothidium</i> cf. <i>lemmermannii</i> (Hustedt) E. Morales	Pl. 18; Fig. 29	PLEM	5	very sensitive	2	Medium indication value
<i>Planothidium</i> cf. <i>polaris</i> (Østrup) A. Witkowski	Pl. 18; Fig. 30	PTPO	2.2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Planothidium</i> sp. 1	Pl. 18; Fig. 28	PLTD sp1	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Planothidium</i> sp. 2	Pl. 18; Fig. 33	PLTD sp2	0	n.a.	0	n.a.

Species	Figures	Codes OMNIDIA	IPS (s)	Sensitivity class	IPS (v)	Indicator value
<i>Pleurosigma angulatum</i> (J.T.Quekett) W.Smith	Pl. 29; Fig. 1	PANG	2.6	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Pleurosigma inflatum</i> Shadbolt	Pl. 29; Fig. 4-5	PIFT	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Pleurosigma</i> cf. <i>salinarum</i> (Grunow) Grunow	Pl. 29; Fig. 2-3	PSAL	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Pleurosira laevis</i> (Ehrenberg) Compère	Pl. 12; Fig. 3-4	PLEV	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Podosira stelligera</i> (Bailey) A.Mann	Pl. 2; Fig. 1-2	POST	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Prestauroneis protractoides</i> (Hustedt) Q.Liu & Kociolek	Pl. 25; Fig. 4	PPRD	2.6	tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Psammodyctyon mediterraneum</i> (Hustedt) D.G.Mann	Pl. 33; Fig. 12	PSMM nw	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Psammodyctyon panduriforme</i> var. <i>continuum</i> (Grunow) Snoeijis	Pl. 33; Fig. 9-11	PPFC	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Psammodyctyon</i> sp. 1	Pl. 33; Fig. 8	PSDT sp1	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Psammodyscus nitidus</i> (W.Gregory) Round & D.G.Mann	Pl. 15; Fig. 1	PNIT	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Pseudofalacia tenera</i> (Hustedt) Y.Liu, Kociolek & Q.Wang	Pl. 26; Fig. 10-11	PFTN	3	somewhat tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Pseudostaurasira brevistriata</i> (Grunow) D.M.Williams & Round	Pl. 13; Fig. 5	PSBR	3	somewhat tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Pseudostaurasira parasitica</i> (W.Smith) E.Morales	Pl. 13; Fig. 31	PPRS	4	sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Pseudostaurasira parasitica</i> var. <i>subconstricta</i> (Grunow) E.Morales	Pl. 13; Fig. 32	PPSC	4	sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Reimeria sinuata</i> (W.Gregory) Kociolek & Stoermer	Pl. 17; Fig. 10	RSIN	4.8	sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Rhaphoneis amphiceros</i> (Ehrenberg) Ehrenberg	Pl. 15; Fig. 2-4	RAMP	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Scolioneis tumida</i> (Brébisson ex Kützing) D.G.Mann	Pl. 20; Fig. 11	STUM	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Sellaphora atomoides</i> (Grunow) Wetzel & Van de Vijver	Pl. 26; Fig. 23-24	SEAT	2.2	tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Sellaphora nigri</i> (De Notaris) C.E.Wetzel & L.Ector	Pl. 26; Fig. 16-20	SNIG	2.2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Sellaphora</i> cf. <i>pseudopupula</i> (Kraske) Lange-Bertalot	Pl. 26; Fig. 22	SPPU	2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Sellaphora pupula</i> (Kützing) Mereschkovsky	Pl. 26; Fig. 12	SPUP	2.6	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Sellaphora</i> cf. <i>saugerresii</i> (Desmazières) C.E.Wetzel & D.G.Mann	Pl. 26; Fig. 13-15	SSGE	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Sellaphora</i> sp. 1	Pl. 26; Fig. 21	SELL sp1	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Simonsenia</i> sp. 1	Pl. 30; Fig. 1	SIMO sp1	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Skeletonema</i> spp.	Pl. 1; Fig. 4-8	SKSP	1.8	very tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Stauriforma</i> cf. <i>exiguiformis</i> (Lange-Bertalot) R.J.Flower, V.J.Jones & Round	Pl. 13; Fig. 33	SEXG	5	very sensitive	2	Medium indication value
<i>Stauroneis</i> cf. <i>kriegeri</i> R.M.Patrick	Pl. 25; Fig. 3	STKR	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Stauroneis</i> cf. <i>marina</i> Hustedt	Pl. 25; Fig. 1	STMA	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Stauroneis</i> sp. 1	Pl. 25; Fig. 2	STAU sp1	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Staurophora</i> cf. <i>amphioxys</i> (W.Gregory) D.G.Mann	Pl. 16; Fig. 6-7	SAXY	2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value

Species	Figures	Codes OMNIDIA	IPS (s)	Sensitivity class	IPS (v)	Indicator value
<i>Staurophora salina</i> (W.Smith) Mereschkowsky	Pl. 16; Fig. 8-9	SPHS	2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Staurosira construens</i> Ehrenberg	Pl. 13; Fig. 21-22	SCON	4	sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Staurosira construens</i> var. <i>binodis</i> (Ehrenberg) P.B.Hamilton	Pl. 13; Fig. 25	SCBI	4	sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Staurosira construens</i> f. <i>subsalina</i> (Hustedt) Bukhtiyarova	Pl. 13; Fig. 24	SCSL	3	somewhat tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Staurosira construens</i> var. <i>venter</i> (Ehrenberg) P.B.Hamilton	Pl. 13; Fig. 23	SCVE	4	sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Staurosirella martyi</i> (Héribaud-Joseph) E.Morales & K.M.Manoylov	Pl. 13; Fig. 27	SLMA	4	sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Staurosirella oldenburgiana</i> (Hustedt) Morales	Pl. 13; Fig. 26	SOLD	4.5	sensitive	2	Medium indication value
<i>Staurosirella</i> cf. <i>pinnata</i> (Ehrenberg) D.M.Williams & Round	Pl. 13; Fig. 28-30	SPIN	4	sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Stephanodiscus hantzschii</i> Grunow	Pl. 6; Fig. 16-18	SHAN	1.8	very tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Stephanodiscus hantzschii</i> f. <i>tenuis</i> (Hustedt) Håkansson & Stoermer	Pl. 6; Fig. 19-21	SHTE	3	somewhat tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Stephanodiscus parvus</i> Stoermer & Håkansson	Pl. 6; Fig. 22-23	SPAV	3	somewhat tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Surirella atomus</i> Hustedt	Pl. 40; Fig. 4-5	SATO	3	somewhat tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Surirella brebissonii</i> Krammer & Lange-Bertalot	Pl. 38; Fig. 1-2	SBRE	3	somewhat tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Surirella curvifacies</i> Brun	Pl. 40; Fig. 3	SCUR	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Surirella fastuosa</i> (Ehrenberg) Ehrenberg	Pl. 41; Fig. 2	SFAS	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Surirella</i> cf. <i>turgida</i> W.Smith	Pl. 40; Fig. 1	STUR	4	sensitive	3	High indication value
<i>Surirella</i> sp. 1	Pl. 38; Fig. 5-7	SURI sp1	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Surirella</i> sp. 2	Pl. 41; Fig. 2	SURI sp2	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Surirella</i> sp. 3	Pl. 39; Fig. 1-2	SURI sp3	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Surirella</i> sp. 4	Pl. 38; Fig. 3-4	SURI sp4	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Tabularia fasciculata</i> (C.Agardh) D.M.Williams & Round	Pl. 14; Fig. 3	TFAS	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Tabularia investiens</i> (W.Smith) D.M.Williams & Round	Pl. 13; Fig. 34	TINV	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Tabularia tabulata</i> (C.Agardh) Snoeijis	Pl. 14; Fig. 4	TTAB	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Thalassio cylus lucens</i> (Hustedt) Håkansson & Mahood	Pl. 5; Fig. 19	TLUC	2.5	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Thalassionema nitzschioides</i> (Grunow) Mereschkowsky	Pl. 5; Fig. 5	THNI	1	very tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Thalassiosira</i> cf. <i>angulata</i> (W.Gregory) Hasle	Pl. 4; Fig. 1-3	THAG	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Thalassiosira baltica</i> (Grunow) Ostentfeld	Pl. 1; Fig. 3	TBAL	2.6	tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Thalassiosira decipiens</i> (Grunow ex Van Heurck) E.G.Jørgensen	Pl. 4; Fig. 4-7	TDEC	2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Thalassiosira eccentrica</i> (Ehrenberg) Cleve	Pl. 3; Fig. 2-3	THEC	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Thalassiosira lacustris</i> (Grunow) Hasle	Pl. 3; Fig. 4-5	THLA	3	somewhat tolerant	3	High indication value

Species	Figures	Codes OMNIDIA	IPS (s)	Sensitivity class	IPS (v)	Indicator value
<i>Thalassiosira mediterranea</i> (Schröder) Hasle	Pl. 5; Fig. 8-11	TMED	2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Thalassiosira minima</i> Gaarder	Pl. 5; Fig. 1	TMIN	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Thalassiosira proschkiniae</i> Makarova	Pl. 5; Fig. 6-7	TPRK	2.3	tolerant	1	Low indication value
<i>Thalassiosira punctigera</i> (Castracane) Hasle	Pl. 5; Fig. 17-18	TPUN	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Thalassiosira</i> cf. <i>simplex</i> Hustedt	Pl. 4; Fig. 8	THLS nw	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Thalassiosira tealata</i> Takano	Pl. 5; Fig. 4-5	TTEA nw	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Thalassiosira tenera</i> Proschkina-Lavrenko	Pl. 4; Fig. 9-10	TTEN	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Thalassiosira</i> sp. 1	Pl. 4; Fig. 11-12	THAL sp1	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Thalassiosira</i> sp. 2	Pl. 5; Fig. 12-14	THAL sp2	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Thalassiosira</i> sp. 3	Pl. 5; Fig. 15-16	THAL sp3	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Thalassiosira</i> sp. 4	Pl. 3; Fig. 1	THAL sp4	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Thalassiosira</i> sp. 5	Pl. 5; Fig. 2-3	THAL sp5	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Triceratium fавus</i> Ehrenberg	Pl. 7; Fig. 8	TFAV	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Tryblionella apiculata</i> Gregory	Pl. 34; Fig. 12-13	TAPI	2.4	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Tryblionella balatonis</i> (Grunow) D.G.Mann	Pl. 33; Fig. 13-14	TRBA	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Tryblionella calida</i> (Grunow) D.G.Mann	Pl. 34; Fig. 8-10	TCAL	2.3	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Tryblionella calida</i> (Grunow) D.G.Mann	Pl. 34; Fig. 8-10	TCAL	2.3	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Tryblionella circumscuta</i> (Bailey) Ralfs	Pl. 35; Fig. 1	TCIR	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Tryblionella</i> cf. <i>debilis</i> Arnott ex O'Meara	Pl. 31; Fig. 13	TDEB	2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Tryblionella gracilis</i> W. Smith	Pl. 35; Fig. 2-3	TGRL	2	tolerant	3	High indication value
<i>Tryblionella hungarica</i> (Grunow) Frenguelli	Pl. 34; Fig. 11	THUN	2.2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Tryblionella levidensis</i> W. Smith	Pl. 34; Fig. 14	TLEV	2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Tryblionella navicularis</i> (Brébisson) Ralfs	Pl. 35; Fig. 4-6	TNAV	2	tolerant	2	Medium indication value
<i>Tryblionella</i> sp. 1	Pl. 33; Fig. 6-7	TRYB sp1	0	n.a.	0	n.a.
<i>Ulnaria delicatissima</i> (W. Smith) Aboal & P.C.Silva	Pl. 14; Fig. 8	UDEL	4	sensitive	1	Low indication value
<i>Zygoceros</i> aff. <i>atlanticus</i> (Frenguelli) Sar	Pl. 10; Fig. 1-3	ZATL	0	n.a.	0	n.a.

Table 4: Morphometric data of diatom taxa. Minimum (median) and maximum values are given when more than 3 valves/frustules were measured. A total of 1142 valves/frustules were measured. Monoraphid species have the size and striae density ranges of the raphe-sternum (RSV) and sternum (SV) valves discriminated. Several species have also densities different categories of striae separated: 1) Amphoroid: dorsal (dors.) and ventral (vent.) striae; 2) *Gyrosigma*: transverse (trans.) and longitudinal (long.) striae; 3) *Pleurosigma*: transverse (trans.) and oblique (obli.) striae. In *Simonsenia*, costae instead of striae were measured. In *Aulacoseira* valve and mantle areolae densities are indicated when measured and placed in different columns.

Species	Length (µm)	Width (µm)	Pervalvar axis (µm)	Striae / Costae in 10 µm	Fibulae / Fibular partitions / Rimoportulae in 10 µm	Lineolae / Mantle areolae in 10 µm	# measured frustules
<i>Achnanthisdium cf. druartii</i>	6.2 (8.7) 11.3	2.5 (3.2) 3.9		24 (27) 34			12
<i>Achnanthisdium exiguum</i>	11.8	3.1		40			1
<i>Achnanthisdium cf. saprophilum</i>	12.2 - 13.6	3.7 - 4.0		27 - 28			2
<i>Achnanthisdium cf. subhudsonis</i>	6.3 - 10.7	2.9 - 3.9		21 - 23			2
<i>Achnanthisdium sp. 1</i>	7.2	3.0		24			1
<i>Achnanthisdium sp. 2</i>	18 (18.5) 26.4	5.1 (5.1) 5.5		18 (20) 21			3
<i>Achnanthisdium sp. 3</i>	12.2 (13) 13.5	4.9 (5.4) 6.1		22 (22) 24			3
<i>Achnanthisdium sp. 4</i>	9.3 (11.1) 12.5	2.9 (3.3) 4.4		21 (25) 28			5
<i>Achnanthisdium sp. 5</i>	8.4 - 9.8	3.5 - 3.6		17 - 18			2
<i>Actinocyclus normanii</i>	33.4					10	1
<i>Actinocyclus octonarius var. tenellus</i>	34.4 - 47.3						2
<i>Actinoptychus senarius</i>	60.2						1
<i>Adlafia sp. 1</i>	7.2	3.4		27			1
<i>Amphora cf. copulata</i> (sensu Sabbe 1997)	22.4 (23.1) 24.2	5.3 (5.8) 6.3		13 (14) 15 (dors.) 13 (14) 16 (vent.)			4
<i>Amphora cf. helenensis</i>	10.5 (13.5) 15.5	5.3 (5.8) 6.4		19 (21) 22 (dors.) 18 (20) 23 (vent.)			5
<i>Amphora cf. indistincta</i>	12.2 (15.1) 26.5	3.4 (3.8) 5.0		14 (15) 19 (dors.) 13 (15) 19 (vent.)			5
<i>Amphora ovalis</i>	30.5 (51.9) 107.4	7.9 (15.1) 21.4		10 (11) 14 (dors.) 9 (9) 10 (vent.)		8	6
<i>Amphora pediculus</i>	7.9 (15.4) 16.9	2.6 (4.4) 4.5		17 (18) 20 (dors.) 15 (18) 22 (vent.)			3
<i>Amphora cf. subacutiuscula</i>	15.5 (20.4) 23.2	3.9 (4.2) 5.3		21 (23) 26 (dors.)			9

Species	Length (µm)	Width (µm)	Pervalvar axis (µm)	Striae / Costae in 10 µm	Fibulae / Fibular partitions / Rimoportulae in 10 µm	Lineolae / Mantle areolae in 10 µm	# measured frustules
<i>Amphora</i> aff. <i>pediculus</i>	9.4 - 13.6	3.4 - 4.1		16 (dors.) 13 - 16 (vent.)			2
<i>Amphora</i> cf. <i>vetula</i>	17.7 (26.3) 34.7	5.3 (5.9) 9.8		11 (13) 15 (dors.) 12 (13) 15 (vent.)		11	11
<i>Anomooneis sphaerophora</i>	71.6	19.5		17			1
<i>Anorthoneis</i> cf. <i>tenuis</i>	15.5	10.1		12		16	1
<i>Asterionella formosa</i>	56.5 - 75.2	2.3 - 2.5		21 - 26			2
<i>Asteromphalus fiabellatus</i>	38.8	31.4		16			1
<i>Aulacoseira ambigua</i>	3.3 (4.3) 5.8		16 (21.9) 26.1			16 (20) 25 (mantle)	7
<i>Aulacoseira brasiliensis</i>	12.9 (13.9) 14.4		12.2	10 (12) 13 (valve areolae)		11 - 16 (mantle)	3
<i>Aulacoseira granulata</i>	5.9 - 6.3		27 - 27.7			12 - 13 (mantle)	2
<i>Aulacoseira islandica</i>	6 (7.8) 10		25.2	26 (valve areolae)		9 (12) 13 (mantle)	4
<i>Aulacoseira pusilla</i>	5.2 (6.6) 8.1		7.5 - 9.3			20 (24) 25 (mantle)	10
<i>Aulacoseira subartica</i>	4.8 (6.5) 9.7		14.5 (15.4) 22			17 (19) 19 (mantle)	8
<i>Bacillaria paxillifera</i>	73.9	6.5		20	9		1
<i>Belonastrum berolinense</i>	19.5 (21.7) 26.6	2.3 (2.6) 3.1	2.8	13 (14) 14			5
<i>Berkeleya fennica</i>	21.1 (29.7) 36.2	4.6 (5.5) 7.3		21 (26) 30			8
<i>Biremis lucens</i>	14.8	4.6		11			1
<i>Brockmanniella brockmannii</i>	10.1 (16.7) 20.0	3.0 (3.8) 4.0		14 (14) 15			6
<i>Caloneis aemula</i>	28.1	7.3		20			1
<i>Caloneis schumanniana</i>	68.7	13.4		16			1
<i>Caloneis westii</i>	96 - 140	21.1 - 23		13			2
<i>Cavinula</i> cf. <i>lapidosa</i>	15.9	6.1		28			1
<i>Catenula adhaerens</i>	13.7	3.1					1

Species	Length (µm)	Width (µm)	Pervalvar axis (µm)	Striae / Costae in 10 µm	Fibulae / Fibular partitions / Rimoportulae in 10 µm	Lineolae / Mantle areolae in 10 µm	# measured frustules
<i>Cavinula cf. lapidosa</i>	15.9	6.1		28			1
<i>Cerataulus smithii</i>	36.1 (44.6) 60.6	34.7 (41.8) 62.6				4 (6) 8	4
<i>Chaetoceros</i> spp.	6.5 (8.0) 11.2	3.1 (5.4) 6.9					8
<i>Climaconeis fasciculata</i>	204 - 220	14.4 - 16.1		15 - 16			2
<i>Cocconeis disculus</i>	9.8 - 13.4 (SV)	5.6 - 7.2 (SV)		11 (SV)		9 (SV)	2
<i>Cocconeis lineata</i>	20.9 - 23.5	13 - 14.5		24 - 25		10 - 14 (SV)	2
<i>Cocconeis cf. neothumensis</i>	7.1 - 9.5 (SV)	4.2 - 5.1 (SV)		20 (SV)		18 - 21 (SV)	2
<i>Cocconeis pediculus</i>	23.9 - 26.1 (SV) 25.3 - 27.7 (RSV)	19.1 - 19.3 (SV) 19.5 - 22.3 (RSV)		20 (SV) 16 - 18 (RSV)		20 (SV) 20 (RSV)	4
<i>Cocconeis placentula</i> var. <i>euglypta</i>	12.1 (16.1) 22.6 (SV) 15.6 (18.1) 22.8 (RSV)	6.4 (9.4) 18.5 (SV) 15.6 (18.1) 22.8 (RSV)		21 (22) 25 (SV) 19 (21) 23 (RSV)		7 (11) 14 (SV)	15
<i>Cocconeis scutellum</i>	12.2 - 26.5 (SV)	7.8 - 17.2 (SV)		12 (SV)		10-16 (SV)	2
<i>Cocconeis stauroneiformis</i>	16.7 (RSV)	9.7 (RSV)		9 (RSV)		19 (RSV)	1
<i>Cocconeis</i> sp. 1	7.0	4.6		25			1
<i>Coscinodiscus jonesianus</i>	76.2 (81.2) 86.4					4 (4) 5	3
<i>Craticula subminuscula</i>	9.3 (9.6) 10.7	4.6 (4.7) 5.0		19 (23) 28			4
<i>Ctenophora pulchella</i> var. <i>lanceolata</i>	10.1 (16.7) 20.0	3.0 (3.8) 4.0		14 (15) 15			6
<i>Cyclostephanos invisitatus</i>	6.9 (8.5) 10.6			21 (24) 26			4
<i>Cyclotella</i> cf. <i>atomus</i> var. <i>gracilis</i>	4.5 (6.1) 6.8			20 (22) 24	7 (8) 10		7
<i>Cyclotella</i> cf. <i>choctawhatcheeana</i>	8.6 (8.9) 12.5			21 - 25			4
<i>Cyclotella</i> cf. <i>meduanae</i>	6.3 (7.7) 11.7			10 (12) 15			8
<i>Cyclotella meneghiniana</i>	21.2			8			1
<i>Cyclotella</i> sp. 1	10.5	9.8		11			1
<i>Cyclotella</i> sp. 2	4.9			24			1
<i>Cylindrotheca gracilis</i>	80.1 (85.8) 94.6	3.5 (4.3) 4.3			19 (20) 21		3
<i>Cylindrotheca closterium</i>	55.4	4.5			19		1

Species	Length (µm)	Width (µm)	Pervalvar axis (µm)	Striae / Costae in 10 µm	Fibulae / Fibular partitions / Rimoportulae in 10 µm	Lineolae / Mantle areolae in 10 µm	# measured frustules
<i>Cymatopleura elliptica</i>	39.7 (61.5) 106.8	26.3 (41.0) 66.8		18 (22) 33	3 (4) 4		3
<i>Cymatopleura solea</i>	157.9	33.2		22	7		1
<i>Cymatosira belgica</i>	14.4	4.1		9			1
<i>Cymbella tumida</i>	58.7	17.9		10 (dors.) 11 (vent.)		23	1
<i>Cymbella</i> sp. 1	31.9	8.8		12 (dors.) 11 (vent.)			1
<i>Cymbella</i> sp. 2	69.9	15.2		12 (dors.) 11 (vent.)		20	1
<i>Cymbopleura</i> cf. <i>amphicephala</i>	29 - 32.2	9.6 - 11.6		10 (dors.) 8 (vent.)			2
<i>Delphineis minutissima</i>	4.2 (6.3) 20.7	3.4 (5.0) 8.7		11 (16) 17		13 (14) 14	7
<i>Delphineis surirelloides</i>	25.6	5.2		15		18	1
<i>Denticula subtilis</i>	8.5 - 11.0	2.8 - 3.1			8		2
<i>Diademsis confervacea</i>	18.4 - 20.5	6.7 - 8.6		21 - 22			2
<i>Diploneis aestuarii</i>	67.9 - 68.1	25.7 - 29.7		9			2
<i>Diploneis schmidtii</i>	16.8	6.9		15			1
<i>Diploneis</i> cf. <i>vacilans</i>	26.7 - 43	10.1 - 17.6		12		18	2
<i>Diploneis vetula</i>	30.0	9.8		14			1
<i>Diploneis weissflogii</i>	22.5 (28.2) 29.9	10.2 (11.1) 12		9 (10) 11			3
<i>Diploneis</i> sp. 1	30.0	9.8		14			1
<i>Discostella pseudostelligera</i>	4.7 (5.8) 6.8			22 (24) 26			9
<i>Discostella stelligera</i> var. <i>tenuis</i>	7.7 (7.7) 8.9			15 (18) 24			3
<i>Discostella</i> cf. <i>waltereckii</i>	6.2 (6.6) 6.8			21 (22) 23			3
<i>Encyonema</i> sp. 1	26.4	9.1		12 (dors.) 14 (vent.)			1
<i>Entomoneis alata</i>	59.7 (64.3) 68.3	23.4 - 23.6		15 (17) 19		23 - 26	3
<i>Entomoneis paludosa</i>	35.1			21			1
<i>Eolimna</i> sp. 1	10.0	4.4		19			1

Species	Length (µm)	Width (µm)	Pervalvar axis (µm)	Striae / Costae in 10 µm	Fibulae / Fibular partitions / Rimoportulae in 10 µm	Lineolae / Mantle areolae in 10 µm	# measured frustules
<i>Epithemia adnata</i>	55.0	11.0		12	3		1
<i>Epithemia sorex</i>	55.0	11.0		12	3		1
<i>Eunotia cf. minor</i>	26.3	7.5		11			1
<i>Eunotia</i> sp. 1	13.9			21			1
<i>Eunotogramma cf. dubium</i>	13.3 (13.5)	4.5	5.7 - 6.5	4			3
<i>Fallacia amphipleuroides</i>	7.6	4.6		26			1
<i>Fallacia helensis</i>	20.1	4.7		25			1
<i>Fallacia margino-punctata</i>	8.4	3.8		20			1
<i>Fallacia</i> cf. ny	17.8	9.1		16			1
<i>Fallacia pygmaea</i>	27.1	10.9		24			1
<i>Fallacia scaldensis</i>	13.7	7.3		21			1
<i>Fallacia</i> cf. wuestii	10.7	4.7		15			1
<i>Fallacia</i> sp. 1	26.9 - 29.4	10.9 - 11.2		21 - 25			2
<i>Fistulifera saprophila</i>	7.1 (7.6) 7.8	3 (3.3) 3.8					3
<i>Fragilaria</i> cf. <i>improbula</i>	6.4 (9.2) 18.2	4.3 (4.7) 5.0		13 (15) 17			4
<i>Fragilaria</i> cf. <i>capucina</i>	18 (21.5) 25.8	3.8 (4.2) 5		11 (12) 15			5
<i>Fragilaria tenera</i> var. <i>nanana</i>	64.6 - 68.9	2.5 - 3		18 - 24			2
<i>Fragilaria</i> sensu lato (s.l.) sp. 1	6.9	2.5		24			1
<i>Fragilaria</i> s.l. sp. 2	4.8 (4.9) 5.2	1.8 (1.8) 1.9	2.4	19			3
<i>Fragilaria</i> s.l. sp. 3	5.8 (9.6) 12.6	3.2 (4.3) 4.7	1.9 - 3	12 (14) 16			14
<i>Fragilaria</i> s.l. sp. 4	6.1 (6.7) 7.5	4 (4.3) 4.5	5	10 (10) 11			4
<i>Fragilaria</i> s.l. sp. 5	15.4	3.3		16			1
<i>Frustulia interposita</i>	138.0	25.1		19 (trans-) 17 (long.)			1
<i>Gedaniella flavovirens</i>	6.4 (9.2) 18.4	4.3 (4.7) 5.0		13 (15) 17		22	4
<i>Geissleria decussis</i>	26.1	8.0		15			1

Species	Length (µm)	Width (µm)	Pervalvar axis (µm)	Striae / Costae in 10 µm	Fibulae / Fibular partitions / Rimoportulae in 10 µm	Lineolae / Mantle areolae in 10 µm	# measured frustules
<i>Gomphonema</i> sp. 1	15.7 (21.2) 28.8	4.8 (5.5) 7.2		11 (14) 15			4
<i>Gomphonema</i> sp. 2	16.4 - 23.8	6.7 - 8.1		12 - 14			2
<i>Gomphonema</i> sp. 3	19.8 - 36.7	5.0 - 6.7		13			2
<i>Gomphonema</i> sp. 4	27.3	7.7		12			1
<i>Gomphonema</i> sp. 5	34.5	7.3		15			1
<i>Gomphonema</i> sp. 6	14.6 - 16.1	4.3 - 4.8		14			2
<i>Gomphonema</i> sp. 7	19.8 - 22.2	4.2 - 4.5		12 - 13			2
<i>Grunowia tabellaria</i>	21.0	7.5		20	8		1
<i>Gyrosigma acuminatum</i> var. <i>gallicum</i>	107.5 (127.2) 148	15.8 (19.4) 22.5		20 (22) 23 (trans.) 18 (19) 19 (long.)			5
<i>Gyrosigma attenuatum</i>	136.5 (184.2) 278.3	23.5 (28.8) 33		14 (trans.) 10 (12) 12 (long.)			5
<i>Gyrosigma balticum</i>	455.4	32.7		12 (trans.) 12 (long.)			1
<i>Gyrosigma eximium</i>	60.7 (65.3) 81.5	10.1 (10.9) 12		20 (21) 21 (trans.) 26 (26) 27 (long.)			3
<i>Gyrosigma fasciola</i>	98.8 - 105.1	12.9 - 13		20 - 21 (trans.) 18 - 19 (long.)			2
<i>Gyrosigma limosum</i>	71.2 (112.2) 127.7	9 (11.1) 12.7		20 (22) 24 (trans.) 24 (27) 29 (long.)			12
<i>Gyrosigma macrum</i>	114.2 - 219.1	12.1 - 13.2		18 (trans.) 30 (long.)			2
<i>Gyrosigma scalproides</i>	84.6	11.5		20 - 23 (trans.) 28 - 30 (long.)			2
<i>Gyrosigma wansbeckii</i>	128.9	15.4		18 (trans.) 18 (long.)			1
<i>Halamphora</i> cf. <i>abuensis</i>	14.3 (17.0) 19.5	2.5 (3.9) 4.4		20 (21) 21 (dors.)			4
<i>Halamphora</i> sp. 1	29.2 (33.9) 34.1	5.2 (5.2) 5.6		15 (15) 15 (dors.) 20 (22) 23 (vent.)			3

Species	Length (µm)	Width (µm)	Pervalvar axis (µm)	Striae / Costae in 10 µm	Fibulae / Fibular partitions / Rimoportulae in 10 µm	Lineolae / Mantle areolae in 10 µm	# measured frustules
<i>Halamphora</i> sp. 2	14.2 (15.8) 17.7	4.0 (4.2) 4.6		16 (18) 20 (dors.) 24 (24) 24 (vent.)			3
<i>Halamphora</i> sp. 3	25.0	4.4		17			1
<i>Hantzschia amphioxys</i>	54.8 - 66.6	8.1 - 10.1		19	7		2
<i>Haslea nipkowii</i>	140 (141.2) 146.2	21.6 (23.1) 28.5		22 (22) 25 (trans.) 28 (28) 29 (long.)			3
<i>Hippodonta caotica</i>	7.6	3.5		15			1
<i>Hippodonta hungarica</i>	14.8 (18.8) 29.2	5.5 (6.1) 7.2		8 (10) 10		33	3
<i>Hippodonta linearis</i>	18.5	7.1		9			1
<i>Humidophila contenta</i>	11.5	3.0					1
<i>Karayevia amoena</i>	14.9 (15.4) 15.8	4.8 (6.1) 5.1		15 (16) 19			3
<i>Karayevia clevei</i>	15.9 (16) 16.4	6.1 (6.2) 6.5		12 (13) 21		21 (21) 23	3
<i>Lindavia comta</i>	9.4 (17.8) 20.3			25 (27) 28			4
<i>Lithodesmium undulatum</i>	36.5 - 52.3	36.5		39		15	2
<i>Luticola frequentissima</i>	9.3 (11.8) 13.9	5.7 (6.1) 7.1		21 (21) 22			5
<i>Luticola goeppertiana</i>	16 (25.6) 29.4	6.7 (7.8) 8.3		17 (18) 18			4
<i>Mastogloia baltica</i>	46.6	11.1		15			1
<i>Mastogloia</i> cf. <i>danseyi</i>	30.2 - 47.3	10.4 - 11.9		14 - 17		19	2
<i>Mayamaea atomus</i>	11.2	4.9		23			2
<i>Mayamaea</i> cf. <i>excelsa</i>	8.3 - 9.3	3.3 - 4.5		19			2
<i>Meloneis mimallis</i>	14.8	4.7		11		9	1
<i>Melosira lineata</i>	15.9 (18.9) 20.4						6
<i>Melosira nummuloides</i>	9.2 - 13.7	11.6					2
<i>Melosira moniliformis</i>	29.1 (29.9) 31.9						3
<i>Melosira varians</i>	15.4 (18.2) 27	21-23					3
<i>Melosira</i> sp. 1	29.0						1

Species	Length (μm)	Width (μm)	Pervalvar axis (μm)	Striae / Costae in 10 μm	Fibulae / Fibular partitions / Rimoportulae in 10 μm	Lineolae / Mantle areolae in 10 μm	# measured frustules
<i>Meridion circulare</i>	28.0	6.3		25			1
<i>Navicula cf. abscondita</i>	11 (33.1) 36.7	4.4 (6.7) 7.2		12 (13) 14			12
<i>Navicula Aleksandrae</i>	11 (12) 13.4	4.4 (4.5) 4.7		19 (22) 22			4
<i>Navicula cf. antonii</i>	24.5	10.6		10			1
<i>Navicula cf. arenaria</i>	47.6 (53.4) 58.6	8.3 (8.8) 9.4		10		31	4
<i>Navicula bipustulata</i>	18.6	4.6		12			1
<i>Navicula bozenae</i>	13.3 - 16	3.2 - 4.3		15 - 18			2
<i>Navicula cincta</i>	19.9 - 20.3	6 - 6.6		10			2
<i>Navicula cf. cryptotenella</i>	18.9 - 32	5 - 6.3		14 - 15			2
<i>Navicula digitoradiata</i>	18.7 (25.4) 29.2	6.1 (6.8) 7.8		11 (12) 13			4
<i>Navicula dilucida</i>	21.3	3.6		22			1
<i>Navicula erifuga</i>	24.75 (29.9) 36.4	5.6 (6.5) 7.6		13 (14) 8		27 (29) 30	8
<i>Navicula cf. flagellifera</i>	28.5 (29.7) 46.8	5.9 (6.7) 7.1		15 (16) 17			12
<i>Navicula gregaria</i> [morphotype 1]	23.2 - 29.1	6.5 - 7.4		17 - 18		30	2
<i>Navicula gregaria</i> [morphotype 2]	23.8	7.1		16			1
<i>Navicula lanceolata</i>	37.7 (44.4) 57.3	10.3 (11.1) 11.1		10 (12) 13			4
<i>Navicula microdigitoradiata</i>	13.9 (20.7) 28	4.6 (5.4) 6.1		15 (16) 18		31	7
<i>Navicula pargemina</i>	19.4 (20.7) 23	3 (4.1) 4.4		19 (19) 20			7
<i>Navicula cf. pargemina</i>	12.7 (14.7) 19.3	1.8 (2.7) 4.5	2.7 (3.6) 5.2	19 (23) 27			25
<i>Navicula peregrina</i>	93.0	19.2		6		20	1
<i>Navicula perminuta</i>	7.4 (12.4) 14.4	2.9 (3.7) 4		14 (17) 18			7
<i>Navicula phyllepta</i>	18.7 - 23.8	5.4 - 6.1		17			2
<i>Navicula cf. phyllepta</i> [morphotype 1]	14.7 (15.4) 15.8	5.4.5 (4.7) 4.7		21 (22) 23			3
<i>Navicula cf. phyllepta</i> [morphotype 2]	18.8 (23.4) 26.1	4.9 (5.4) 5.5		18 (19) 19			6

Species	Length (µm)	Width (µm)	Pervalvar axis (µm)	Striae / Costae in 10 µm	Fibulae / Fibular partitions / Rimoportulae in 10 µm	Lineolae / Mantle areolae in 10 µm	# measured frustules
<i>Navicula cf. salinarum</i>	23.9 - 30.3	8.5 - 10.1		12 - 14			2
<i>Navicula salinicola</i>	10.6 (10.7) 11	3.2 - 3.3		19 (19) 20			3
<i>Navicula cf. salinicola</i>	11.4 (13.9) 16.1	2.7 (3.3) 4.4		18 (20) 22			17
<i>Navicula slesvicensis</i>	47.4	10.4		9		26	1
<i>Navicula spartinetensis</i>	21.6 (28.3) 40	5.2 (6.1) 6.9		12 (12) 14		21 (23) 25	10
<i>Navicula cf. starmachiooides</i>	11.8 (11.8) 12.7	2.9 (3.2) 3.4		15 (15) 18			3
<i>Navicula tripunctata</i>	27.6 (42) 48.2	4.8 (8.5) 9.2		9 (11) 11			3
<i>Navicula cf. utlandshoerriensis</i>	11.1 (16.7) 24.7	3.6 (6.3) 6.7		13 - 15			3
<i>Navicula veneta</i>	23.2	5.2		15			1
<i>Navicula viminoides</i> subsp. <i>cosmomarina</i>	11.7	5.3		15			1
<i>Navicula wiesneri</i>	26.5 (29.2) 29.3	5.9 - 6		12 (14) 15			3
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 1	25.1 (26.3) 27.5	5.1 (5.2) 5.2		15			2
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 2	9.0	3.5		26			1
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 3	9.4	3.2		16			1
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 4	20.6 (22.5) 24.3	3.8 (4) 4.2		17 (17) 19			3
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 5	19.9 - 25.6	3.8 - 4.4		14			2
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 6	38.3	8.5		13			1
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 7	31.8 (43.3) 44.4	6 (7) 7.1		15 (15) 16			3
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 8	26.1	5.4		19			1
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 9	24.8	4.8		17		30	1
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 10	13.3	3.2		17			1
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 11	14.1 - 14.2	3.5 - 3.6					2
<i>Navicula</i> sl. sp. 1	15.1 - 21.2	6.2 - 7		18 - 19			2
<i>Navicula</i> sl. sp. 2	7.6 (8) 9	1.6 (2) 2.5					10
<i>Navicula</i> sl. sp. 3	27.1	6.9		15			1

Species	Length (µm)	Width (µm)	Pervalvar axis (µm)	Striae / Costae in 10 µm	Fibulae / Fibular partitions / Rimoportulae in 10 µm	Lineolae / Mantle areolae in 10 µm	# measured frustules
<i>Nitzschia acicularis</i>	54.2 - 59.2	3.3 (3.4) 3.8			18 (18) 19		3
<i>Nitzschia aequorea</i>	15.8 (20.8) 28.1	3.3 (3.9) 4.3			13 (15) 16		11
<i>Nitzschia agnita</i>	42.8 - 45.3	4.1 - 5			16 - 17		2
<i>Nitzschia amphibia</i>	16 (16.5) 21.4	4.4 (4.8) 5.3		16 (17) 18	8 (10) 11		4
<i>Nitzschia angularis</i>	81.9	10.5			4		1
<i>Nitzschia brevissima</i>	32.2 - 59.8	5.5 - 7.5		26	7 - 9		2
<i>Nitzschia cf. capitellata</i>	20.7	3.5			13		1
<i>Nitzschia cf. dissipata</i>	21 (42.7) 53.1	2.8 (5.2) 5.6			6 (6) 9		7
<i>Nitzschia cf. distans</i>	23 (26.3) 43.1	4.1 - 4.6	4		5 (6) 7		4
<i>Nitzschia dubia</i>	69.8	12.2		23	11		1
<i>Nitzschia cf. dubia</i>	200 - 289.2	20.9 - 22		21 - 26	6 - 7	23	2
<i>Nitzschia cf. filiformis</i>	47 (70.1) 72	4.2 (4.6) 4.7		30 - 35	12 (13) 16		3
<i>Nitzschia fonticola</i>	18 - 18.1	3.4 - 3.9		28 - 29	12 - 14		2
<i>Nitzschia frustulum</i>	10.5 (17.1) 26.8	2.8 (3.6) 4.4		21 (27) 28	9 (12) 17		7
<i>Nitzschia cf. gessneri</i>	132.0	6.0		24	14		1
<i>Nitzschia incognita</i>	31.4	3.3		30	12		1
<i>Nitzschia aff. inconspicua</i>	7.2	3.1			10		1
<i>Nitzschia lanceola</i> var. <i>minutula</i>	15.9 - 18.1	4.7 - 5.4		18	10 - 18		2
<i>Nitzschia lorenziana</i>	43.8	3.3		21	11		1
<i>Nitzschia maxima</i>	341.3	11 - 11.3		23 - 24	5 - 6	25	2
<i>Nitzschia microcephala</i>	9.1 - 10.4	4.1			13 - 14		2
<i>Nitzschia nana</i>	35.2	4.2			9		1
<i>Nitzschia ovalis</i>	17.9	5.5			16		1
<i>Nitzschia palea</i>	12.6 (18.6) 23.3	2.7 (3.5) 4.1			10 (12) 13		6

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<i>Nitzschia cf. parvula</i>	26.7	4.4		33	14		1
<i>Nitzschia pellucida</i>	29.5	4.9			12		1
<i>Nitzschia cf. pseudofonticola</i>	38.2	5.0			8		1
<i>Nitzschia cf. pusilla</i>	9.3 (11) 21.6	1.9 (3.7) 4			13 (15) 20		10
<i>Nitzschia recta</i>	55.9	5.2			5		1
<i>Nitzschia rhopalodioides</i>	32.6 - 34.6	6.1 - 7.6			10		2
<i>Nitzschia sigma</i>	48 (101.4) 132.4	4.9 (6.8) 7.8		19 (20) 20	7 (9) 11		5
<i>Nitzschia supralitorea</i>	18 (19.5) 20.7	3.2 (3.4) 4.6		22 - 24	10 (14) 16		3
<i>Nitzschia thermaloides</i>	33.6 (38.9) 48.9	6 (6.7) 7.3			16 (17) 18		9
<i>Nitzschia tubicola</i>	18.7 (26.8) 40.7	2.5 (3.3) 4			12 (14) 15		18
<i>Nitzschia sp. 1</i>	144.1	6.3			9		1
<i>Nitzschia sp. 2</i>	16.8	2.3			12		1
<i>Nitzschia sp. 3</i>	27.5 - 27.5	4.8 - 5.6		30 - 33	9		2
<i>Nitzschia sp. 4</i>	11.6 (13) 13.5	4.1 (4.2) 4.3			9 (10) 11		3
<i>Nitzschia sp. 5</i>	14.1	2.9		27	9		1
<i>Nitzschia sp. 6</i>	43.1	10.7			9		1
<i>Nitzschia sp. 7</i>	45.9 - 46.9	5.5 - 8.1		36	10 - 12		2
<i>Nitzschia sp. 8</i>	42.9 - 44.4	7.3 - 8.3			10 - 12		2
<i>Nupella sp. 1</i>	9.5	2.9					1
<i>Odontella rostrata</i>	12.3 (17.5) 26.7	8.2 (12.3) 16.3			16 (19) 20		9
<i>Opephora horstiana</i>	11.6	2.8		15			1
<i>Opephora mutabilis</i>	6.2 (7.8) 10.5	2.9 (4.6) 5.7	4.2	9 (10) 11			4
<i>Paralia cf. fenestrata</i>	11.2 (14.2) 18.1						5
<i>Paralia sulcata</i>	14.8 (18.8) 29.1	5.5 (6.1) 7.1		125 (10) 10	125 (10) 10		3

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<i>Petrodictyon gemma</i>	102.7	35.2		24			1
<i>Pinnularia divergentissima</i>	29.8	6.3		14			2
<i>Pinnularia</i> sp. 1	68.3 - 78.4	14.3 - 16.3		7 - 8			1
<i>Pinnularia</i> sp. 2	143.4	19.8		6			1
<i>Plagiogrammopsis crawfordii</i>	10.3	3.9		27			1
<i>Plagiogrammopsis minima</i>	6 (6.8) 7.7		4.2 - 4.8	17			3
<i>Plagiogrammopsis vanheurckii</i>	14.6 (16.2) 20.2	4.6	10.1	13			4
<i>Plagiogrammopsis confusum</i>	40.3		30	25		27	1
<i>Plagiotropis seriata</i>	179.2 - 204.1	44.2	44.6	10 - 12		23	2
<i>Plagiotropis</i> cf. <i>vanheurckii</i>	37.8 (40.5) 42.7	7.4	8.4 - 9.1	23 - 24		23	4
<i>Planothidium delicatulum</i>	11.7 (13.3) 15.6	4.1 (5.1) 5.9		14 (15) 10			7
<i>Planothidium frequentissimum</i>	10.3	4.5		15			1
<i>Planothidium hauckianum</i>	5.6 (13.6) 15	3.9 (5.5) 7.133		11 (12) 12			5
<i>Planothidium lanceolatum</i>	11.2 (17.5) 19.6	5.8 (6.0) 6.4		12 (14) 15			3
<i>Planothidium</i> cf. <i>lemmermannii</i>	6.5	3.3		19			1
<i>Planothidium</i> cf. <i>polaris</i>	11.2	5.6		12			1
<i>Planothidium</i> sp. 1	6.9	4.3		17			1
<i>Planothidium</i> sp. 2	13.0	5.9		13			1
<i>Pleurosigma angulatum</i>	196 (236.6) 288.6	39.5 (6.1) 57.8		15 (18) 19 (obli.) 16 (17) 18 (trans.)			4
<i>Pleurosigma inflatum</i>	90.8 - 106.1	17.9 - 21.1		15 - 18 (obli.) 19 - 20 (trans.)			2
<i>Pleurosigma</i> cf. <i>salinarum</i>	104.4 (284) 312	19.5 (46.1) 51.4		15 (16) 17 (obli.) 15 (16) 16 (trans.)			5
<i>Pleurosira laevis</i>	72.1 - 73	62 - 63.7				15	2
<i>Podosira stelligera</i>	40.7 (42.6) 48.5			13 (14) 15			3
<i>Prestauroneis protractoides</i>	20.0	6.5		17			1

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<i>Psammodyctyon mediterraneum</i>	30.7 - 36.2	8.1 - 8.8		17 - 19	12	16	2
<i>Psammodyctyon panduriforme</i> var. <i>continuum</i>	17.6 (21.4) 26.8	7.1 (8.3) 9.9		15 (20) 21	11 (12) 13	14 (17) 19	6
<i>Psammodyctyon</i> sp. 1	23.6	8.0		16		15	1
<i>Psammodiscus nitidus</i>	29.5					5	1
<i>Pseudofallacia tenera</i>	15.9 (16.6) 19.7	6.5 (7.1) 7.5		16 (17) 17			4
<i>Pseudostaurasira brevistriata</i>	5.5 (9.9) 18.1	3.9 (4.6) 5.2		13 (13) 15			3
<i>Pseudostaurasira parasitica</i>	15.8	5.1		19			1
<i>Pseudostaurasira parasitica</i> var. <i>subconstricta</i>	21.5	4.6		20			1
<i>Reimeria sinuata</i>	23.5	5.7		8			1
<i>Rhaphoneis amphiceros</i>	28.9 (39.3) 82.1	18.4 (20.1) 23.2		6 (6) 7		7 (8) 9	4
<i>Scolioneis tumida</i>	112.1	23.8		12		19	1
<i>Sellaphora atomoides</i>	8.2 - 9.6	3.1 - 3.2		24 - 27			2
<i>Sellaphora nigri</i>	6.6 (7.4) 11.7	3.2 (4.0) 4.3		21 (23) 28			10
<i>Sellaphora</i> cf. <i>pseudopupula</i>	22.3	6.4		23			1
<i>Sellaphora pupula</i>	12.7	4.6		21			1
<i>Sellaphora</i> cf. <i>saugerresii</i>	7.3 - 8.8	3.7 - 3.8		22			2
<i>Sellaphora</i> sp. 1	32.2	7.6		15			1
<i>Simonsenia</i> sp. 1	11.2 - 11.5	2.3 - 2.4		28 - 29			2
<i>Skeletonema</i> spp.	3.8 (4.6) 10.3	3.8	4.1 (4.4) 5.3		8 (9) 11		24
<i>Stauroneis</i> cf. <i>kriegeri</i>	21.9	5.5 - 5.7		27			1
<i>Stauroneis</i> cf. <i>marina</i>	26.8	9.0		23			1
<i>Stauriforma</i> cf. <i>exiguiformis</i>	20.0	5.8		17			1
<i>Stauroneis</i> cf. <i>marina</i>	26.8	9.0		23			1
<i>Stauroneis</i> sp. 1	19.3	5.7		22			1

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<i>Staurophora amphioxys</i>	53.6	11.9		17			1
<i>Staurophora salina</i>	39.3 (43) 55.3	10.4 (10.8) 12.7		18 (20) 21			1
<i>Staurosira construens</i>	8.3 (15.9) 21	4.8 (5.9) 11.7		13 (14) 15			5
<i>Staurosira construens</i> var. <i>binodis</i>	17.8	8.3		16			1
<i>Staurosira construens</i> f. <i>subsalina</i>	13.3	5.2		18			1
<i>Staurosira construens</i> var. <i>venter</i>	6.6 (10.3) 11.7	4.8 (5.1) 5.4		15 (16) 16			4
<i>Staurosirella martyi</i>	15.5	4.4		8			1
<i>Staurosirella oldenburgiana</i>	11.5	3.8		14			1
<i>Staurosirella</i> cf. <i>pinnata</i>	6.1 (12.2) 15.2	4.7 (5) 6.7		9 (10) 11			6
<i>Stephanodiscus hantzschii</i>	10.3 (14.8) 19.9			10 (16) 17		18	9
<i>Stephanodiscus hantzschii</i> f. <i>tenuis</i>	10.3 (12.8) 16.3			19			6
<i>Stephanodiscus parvus</i>	6.5 (8.3) 12.3			16 (19) 23			6
<i>Surirella atomus</i>	14.0	8.1			7		1
<i>Surirella brebissonii</i>	22.8 (30) 35	12.7 (17.7) 24.1		14 (17) 21	5		4
<i>Surirella curvifacies</i>	84.5	35.1			2		1
<i>Surirella fastuosa</i>	89.0	63.0		15	2		1
<i>Surirella</i> cf. <i>turgida</i>	89.0	63.0		15	2		1
<i>Surirella</i> sp. 1	14.8 (35.9) 46.3	10.3 (20.6) 23.7		10 (16) 23	2 (4) 6		6
<i>Surirella</i> sp. 2	38.1 - 65.9	8.8 - 14.1			6 - 7		2
<i>Surirella</i> sp. 3	67.4	33.1			2		1
<i>Surirella</i> sp. 4	27 - 30.7	10.7 - 11.8		25	7		2
<i>Tabularia fasciculata</i>	57.4	5.9		14			1
<i>Tabularia investiens</i>	18.4	2.7		10			1
<i>Tabularia tabulata</i>	71.6	6.2		15			1

Species	Length (µm)	Width (µm)	Pervalvar axis (µm)	Striae / Costae in 10 µm	Fibulae / Fibular partitions / Rimoportulae in 10 µm	Lineolae / Mantle areolae in 10 µm	# measured frustules
<i>Thalassiosira lucens</i>	9.5						1
<i>Thalassionema nitzschoides</i>	51.9	3.2	9				1
<i>Thalassiosira cf. angulata</i>	11.1 (15.7) 29.6			5 (7) 11	13 (16) 19		15
<i>Thalassiosira baltica</i>	109.4			3	8		1
<i>Thalassiosira decipiens</i>	8.1 (14.7) 27.7			3 (5) 7	9 (12) 21		21
<i>Thalassiosira eccentrica</i>	22.6 (41.2) 65.9			3	6 (7) 9		17
<i>Thalassiosira lacustris</i>	24.1 - 27.3				10		2
<i>Thalassiosira mediterranea</i>	7.5 (11.2) 21.4			5 (7) 8	30		11
<i>Thalassiosira minima</i>	6.1 (7.6) 9.3			6 (7) 7			7
<i>Thalassiosira proschkinae</i>	6.4 (9) 12.2				18 (24) 25		6
<i>Thalassiosira punctigera</i>	38.4 (53.2) 72.7		15	6 (6) 8	13 (17) 20		4
<i>Thalassiosira cf. simplex</i>	18.3 - 21.2			6 - 8	17		2
<i>Thalassiosira tealata</i>	7.4 (18.8) 9.4			3 (4) 4			3
<i>Thalassiosira tenera</i>	13.1 (19.8) 23.8			6 (6) 7	12 (14) 16		3
<i>Thalassiosira sp. 1</i>	24.1			6	8		1
<i>Thalassiosira sp. 2</i>	8.9 (11.7) 13.7			13 (14) 15	23 (25) 28		4
<i>Thalassiosira sp. 3</i>	20.6		27	3			1
<i>Thalassiosira sp. 4</i>	42.9				13		1
<i>Thalassiosira sp. 5</i>	9.6		24	5			1
<i>Triceratium favus</i>					2		1
<i>Tryblionella apiculata</i>	27.2 (31.5) 43	6.8 (7.2) 8.1	16 (17) 17	16 (17) 17			2
<i>Tryblionella balatonis</i>	9.1 (9.6) 11.9	4.8 (5.1) 5.2	18 (19) 20	18 (18) 19			3
<i>Tryblionella calida</i>	27.7 (48.1) 55.6	8.1 (9.1) 9.5	14 (17) 22	7 (8) 10			5
<i>Tryblionella circumscuta</i>	170 - 173	59 - 63.9	26 - 27	5			2

Species	Length (µm)	Width (µm)	Pervalvar axis (µm)	Striae / Costae in 10 µm	Fibulae / Fibular partitions / Rimoportulae in 10 µm	Lineolae / Mantle areolae in 10 µm	# measured frustules
<i>Tryblionella cf. debilis</i>	15 - 16.8	7.3 - 7.4			12 - 14		2
<i>Tryblionella gracilis</i>	49.5 (67.5) 70.5	14.6 (18.1) 24.7		15 (16) 22	7 (7) 8	8	4
<i>Tryblionella hungarica</i>	47.7 - 48.3	5.2 - 5.8		17 - 19	11		2
<i>Tryblionella levidensis</i>	46.2	16.8			11		1
<i>Tryblionella navicularis</i>	46.4 - 49.2	16.8 - 19.7		7 - 8	7 - 8		2
<i>Tryblionella</i> sp. 1	29.1	10.2		24	11		1
<i>Ulnaria delicatissima</i>	121.0	2.9		13			1
<i>Zygoceros</i> aff. <i>atlanticus</i>	54.7 (70.1) 107.9	37.7 (50.2) 54.5			7 (9) 9		5

Table 5: Ecological preferences of the diatom taxa. Salinity preferences, habitat and growth-form are given for each taxon, as well as the list of references used.

Species	Salinity preferences	Habitat	Growth-form	References on Ecology
<i>Achnanthydium cf. druartii</i>	freshwater	benthos	epilithic	Rimet et al. (2010)
<i>Achnanthydium exiguum</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Round et al. (1990); Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Achnanthydium cf. saprophilum</i>	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Achnanthydium cf. subhudsonis</i>	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Achnanthydium</i> sp. 1	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Round et al. (1990): Freshwater haptobenthic
<i>Achnanthydium</i> sp. 2	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Round et al. (1990): Freshwater haptobenthic
<i>Achnanthydium</i> sp. 3	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Round et al. (1990): Freshwater haptobenthic
<i>Achnanthydium</i> sp. 4	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Round et al. (1990): Freshwater haptobenthic
<i>Achnanthydium</i> sp. 5	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Round et al. (1990): Freshwater haptobenthic
<i>Actinocyclus normanii</i>	brackish	plankton	planktonic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Actinocyclus octonarius</i> var. <i>tenellus</i>	marine	thycoplankton	tychoplanktonic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990): epiphytic on seaweeds often encountered in nearshore plankton; Hendey (1964): in neritic plankton
<i>Actinoptochus senarius</i>	marine	thycoplankton	tychoplanktonic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990): neritic plankton, probably mainly of the assemblage lying loose or attached to other algae on coastal sediments
<i>Adlafia</i> sp. 1	freshwater	benthos	epipelic	Lange-Bertalot et al. (2017)
<i>Amphora</i> cf. <i>copulata</i> (sensu Sabbe)	fresh/brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Amphora</i> cf. <i>helenensis</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipsammic	Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994); Ribeiro et al. (2013)
<i>Amphora</i> cf. <i>indistincta</i>	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Round et al. (1990): epiphytic, epilithic, epipelic
<i>Amphora ovalis</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Amphora</i> aff. <i>pediculus</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994); Ribeiro et al. (2013): epipsammic
<i>Amphora pediculus</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994); Ribeiro et al. (2013): epipsammic
<i>Amphora</i> cf. <i>subacutiuscula</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Round et al. (1990): epiphytic, epilithic epipelic; Ribeiro et al. (2013): epipelic
<i>Aulacoseira ambigua</i>	fresh/brackish	plankton	planktonic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Aulacoseira granulata</i>	fresh/brackish	plankton	planktonic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Aulacoseira islandica</i>	freshwater	plankton	planktonic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Aulacoseira pusilla</i>	freshwater	plankton	planktonic	AlgaeBase (2019); Round et al. (1990): planktonic
<i>Aulacoseira brasiliensis</i>	freshwater	plankton	planktonic	AlgaeBase (2019); Round et al. (1990): planktonic

Species	Salinity preferences	Habitat	Growth-form	References on Ecology
<i>Aulacoseira pusilla</i>	freshwater	plankton	planktonic	AlgaeBase (2019); Round et al. (1990): planktonic
<i>Aulacoseira subartica</i>	freshwater	plankton	planktonic	Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Anomoeoneis sphaerophora</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Bacillaria paxillifera</i>	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Belonastrum berolinense</i>	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	AlgaeBase (2019); Krammer & Lange-Bertalot (1991a); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Berkeleya fennica</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	tube-dwelling	Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Biremis lucens</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipsammic	Denys (1991); Ribeiro et al. (2013): epipsammic
<i>Brockmanniella brockmannii</i>	brackish/marine	thycoplankton	tychoplanktonic	Denys (1991); Sabbe et al. (2010); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Caloneis aemula</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991)
<i>Caloneis schumanniana</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Caloneis westii</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Hendey (1964)
<i>Catenula adhaerens</i>	brackish	benthos	epipsammic	Denys (1991); Ribeiro et al. (2013): epipsammic; Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Cavinula cf. lapidosa</i>	fresh/terrestrial	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990): epipelon, moist subaerial habitats; Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Cerataulus smithii</i>	marine	benthos	epipsammic	Hendey (1964); Round et al. (1990): attached to sand grains, found in plankton but strictly benthic
<i>Chaetoceros</i> spp.	marine	plankton	planktonic	Round et al. (1990): marine, planktonic
<i>Climaconeis fasciculata</i>	marine	benthos	epipelic	Cox (1982); Round et al. (1990): marine, epipelic
<i>Cocconeis disculus</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Cocconeis lineata</i>	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Lange-Bertalot et al. (2017))
<i>Cocconeis cf. neoithumensis</i>	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Lange-Bertalot et al. (2017)
<i>Cocconeis pediculus</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Cocconeis placentula</i> var. <i>euglypta</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Cocconeis lineata</i>	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Lange-Bertalot et al. (2017))
<i>Cocconeis scutellum</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Cocconeis pediculus</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Cocconeis placentula</i> var. <i>euglypta</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Cocconeis stauroneiformis</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Cocconeis</i> sp. 1	brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Round et al. (1990): freshwater to marine. Living in plants, rocks, etc.
<i>Coccinodiscus jonesianus</i>	marine	plankton	planktonic	Hendey (1964); Tomas (1997): warm water region
<i>Craticula subminuscula</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Cocconeis scutellum</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)

Species	Salinity preferences	Habitat	Growth-form	References on Ecology
<i>Ctenophora pulchella</i> var. <i>lanceolata</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Lange-Bertalot et al. (2017); Round et al. (1990): attached to substrata, brackish but also penetrating into freshwater
<i>Cyclostephanos invisitatus</i>	freshwater	plankton	planktonic	AlgaeBase (2019); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Cyclotella</i> cf. <i>atomus</i> var. <i>gracilis</i>	fresh/brackish	plankton	planktonic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Cyclotella</i> cf. <i>choctawhatcheeana</i>	brackish/marine	thycoplankton	tychoplanktonic	Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Cyclotella</i> cf. <i>medusanae</i>	fresh/brackish	plankton	planktonic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Cyclotella meneghiniana</i>	fresh/brackish	thycoplankton	tychoplanktonic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Cyclotella</i> sp. 1	brackish	plankton	planktonic	Round et al. (1990): mainly freshwater and planktonic with two species occurring in shallow coastal waters
<i>Cyclotella</i> sp. 2	brackish	plankton	planktonic	Round et al. (1990): mainly freshwater and planktonic with two species occurring in shallow coastal waters
<i>Cylindrotheca closterium</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Ribeiro et al. (2013); Round et al. (1990): epipelon of marine habitats
<i>Cylindrotheca gracilis</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Ribeiro et al. (2013); Round et al. (1990): epipelon of marine habitats
<i>Cymatopleura elliptica</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Cymatopleura solea</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Cymatosira belgica</i>	brackish	thycoplankton	tychoplanktonic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Cymbella tumida</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Cymbella</i> sp. 1	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Round et al. (1990): Epiphytic, epilithic or epipelic. Freshwater
<i>Cymbella</i> sp. 2	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Round et al. (1990): Epiphytic, epilithic or epipelic. Freshwater
<i>Cymbopleura</i> cf. <i>amphicephala</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Delphineis surirelloides</i>	marine	thycoplankton	tychoplanktonic	Round et al. (1990): epipsammic; Sabbe (1997): restricted to higher salinities, tycho planktonic; Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Denticula subtilis</i>	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Diademsis confervacea</i>	fresh/terrestrial	benthos	haptobenthic	Coste & Ector (2000); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Diploneis aestuarii</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Diploneis schmidtii</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Diploneis</i> cf. <i>vacillans</i>	marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Witkowski et al. (2000)
<i>Diploneis vetula</i>	marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990)
<i>Diploneis weissflogii</i>	marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990)
<i>Diploneis</i> sp. 1	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): predominantly marine but with a few freshwater species
<i>Discostella pseudostelligera</i>	fresh/brackish	plankton	planktonic	AlgaeBase (2019); Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Discostella stelligera</i> var. <i>tenuis</i>	fresh/brackish	plankton	planktonic	AlgaeBase (2019); Denys (1991)
<i>Delphineis minutissima</i>	brackish/marine	thycoplankton	tychoplanktonic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990): epipsammic. Freshwater; Sabbe (1997): abundant and characteristic species in silty sediments of the Westerschelde estuary; tycho planktonic

Species	Salinity preferences	Habitat	Growth-form	References on Ecology
<i>Discostella cf. waltereckii</i>	fresh/brackish	plankton	planktonic	AlgaeBase (2019); Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Encyonema</i> sp. 1	freshwater	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): Freshwater; epiphytic, epilithic, often metaphytic
<i>Entomoneis alata</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Entomoneis paludosa</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Eolimna</i> sp. 1	brackish	benthos	epipelic	AlgaeBase (2019)
<i>Epithemia adnata</i>	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Epithemia sorex</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epiphytic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Eunotia cf. minor</i>	freshwater	benthos	epiphytic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Eunotia</i> sp. 1	freshwater	benthos	epiphytic	Round et al. (1990): restricted to freshwater and particularly abundant in epiphyton and metaphyton of oligotrophic waters
<i>Eunotogramma cf. dubium</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipsammic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Fallacia amphipleuroides</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipsammic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Ribeiro et al. (2013): epipsammic
<i>Fallacia helensis</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990)
<i>Fallacia margino-punctata</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipsammic	Round et al. (1990); Sabbe et al. (1999): epipsammic
<i>Fallacia cf. ny</i>	marine	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); Witkowski et al. (2000): marine tropical form
<i>Fallacia pygmaea</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): groups of marine and freshwater epipelic diatoms. Sabbe et al. (1999): epipelic
<i>Fallacia scaldensis</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): groups of marine and freshwater epipelic diatoms. Sabbe et al. (1999): epipelic
<i>Fallacia cf. wuestii</i>	marine	benthos	epipsammic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994); Sabbe et al. (1999): epipsammic
<i>Fallacia</i> sp. 1	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): groups of marine and freshwater epipelic diatoms
<i>Fistulifera saprophilla</i>	freshwater	benthos	epipelic	Lange-Bertalot et al. (2017); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Fragilaria cf. impróbula</i>	marine	benthos	epipsammic	Witkowski et al. (2000): marine
<i>Fragilaria cf. capucina</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Fragilaria tenera</i> var. <i>nanana</i>	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Fragilaria</i> s.l. sp. 1	brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Lange-Bertalot et al. (2017); Round et al. (1990)
<i>Fragilaria</i> s.l. sp. 2	brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Lange-Bertalot et al. (2017); Round et al. (1990)
<i>Fragilaria</i> s.l. sp. 3	brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Lange-Bertalot et al. (2017); Round et al. (1990)
<i>Fragilaria</i> s.l. sp. 4	brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Lange-Bertalot et al. (2017); Round et al. (1990)
<i>Fragilaria</i> s.l. sp. 5	brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Lange-Bertalot et al. (2017); Round et al. (1990)
<i>Frustulia interposita</i>	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Ribeiro et al. (2013); Round et al. (1990)
<i>Gedaniella flavovirens</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipsammic	Li et al. (2018)
<i>Geissleria decussis</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Van Dam et al. (1994); Ribeiro et al. (2013): epipelic
<i>Gomphonema</i> sp. 1	freshwater	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): very common in freshwater haptobenthic communities

Species	Salinity preferences	Habitat	Growth-form	References on Ecology
<i>Gomphonema</i> sp. 2	freshwater	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): very common in freshwater haptobenthic communities
<i>Gomphonema</i> sp. 3	freshwater	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): very common in freshwater haptobenthic communities
<i>Gomphonema</i> sp. 4	freshwater	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): very common in freshwater haptobenthic communities
<i>Gomphonema</i> sp. 5	freshwater	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): very common in freshwater haptobenthic communities
<i>Grunowia tabellaria</i>	freshwater	benthos	epipelic	Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Gyrosigma acuminatum</i> var. <i>gallicum</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Ribeiro et al. (2013)
<i>Gyrosigma attenuatum</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Gyrosigma balticum</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Gyrosigma eximium</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Gyrosigma fasciola</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Gyrosigma limosum</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Ribeiro et al. (2013)
<i>Gyrosigma macrum</i>	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Gyrosigma scalpoides</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990)
<i>Gyrosigma wansbeckii</i>	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Halamphora</i> cf. <i>abuensis</i>	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Levkov (2009)
<i>Halamphora</i> sp. 1	brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Levkov (2009)
<i>Halamphora</i> sp. 2	brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Levkov (2009)
<i>Halamphora</i> sp. 3	brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Levkov (2009)
<i>Hantzschia amphioxys</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Haslea nipkowii</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Ribeiro (2010)
<i>Hippodonta caotica</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Ribeiro (2010); Pavlov et al. (2013); Witkowski et al. (2000)
<i>Hippodonta hungarica</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Lange-Bertalot (2001); Pavlov et al. (2013)
<i>Hippodonta linearis</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991)
<i>Humidophila contenta</i>	fresh/terrestrial	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Karayevia amoena</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipsammic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Karayevia clevei</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipsammic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Lindavia comta</i>	freshwater	plankton	planktonic	Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Lithodesmium undulatum</i>	marine	plankton	planktonic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990)
<i>Luticola frequentissima</i>	fresh/brackish/terrestrial	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990): fresh and slightly brackish water genus, commonest in soils or subaerial habitats and in estuaries; Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Luticola goeppertiana</i>	fresh/terrestrial	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): fresh and slightly brackish water genus, commonest in soils or subaerial habitats and in estuaries; Van Dam et al. (1994)

Species	Salinity preferences	Habitat	Growth-form	References on Ecology
<i>Mastogloia baltica</i>	marine	benthos	epipelic	Lange-Bertalot et al. (2017); Witkowski et al. (2000)
<i>Mastogloia cf. danseyi</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Hendey (1964)
<i>Mayamaea atomus</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Mayamaea cf. excelsa</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Meloneis mimallis</i>	marine	benthos	epipsammic	Louvrou et al. (2012 (2012))
<i>Melosira lineata</i>	brackish	thycoplankton	tychoplanktonic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Melosira moniliformis</i>	brackish/marine	thycoplankton	tychoplanktonic	Denys (1991); Hendey (1964); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Melosira nummuloides</i>	brackish/marine	thycoplankton	tychoplanktonic	Denys (1991); Hendey (1964); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Melosira varians</i>	fresh/brackish	thycoplankton	tychoplanktonic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Melosira sp. 1</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	haptobenthic	Round et al (1990); common in marine epibenthic habitats
<i>Meridion circulare</i>	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Navicula cf. abscondita</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Sabbe (1997)
<i>Navicula alexandreae</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipsammic	Ribeiro et al. (2013)
<i>Navicula cf. antonii</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994); Lange-Bertalot (2001): eutrophic and hypertrophic waters with average to high electrolyte content
<i>Navicula cf. arenaria</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994); Lange-Bertalot (2001): brackish waters
<i>Navicula bipustulata</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Sabbe (1997)
<i>Navicula bozenae</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipsammic	Ribeiro et al. (2013)
<i>Navicula cincta</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipsammic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994); Sabbe (1997)
<i>Navicula cf. cryptotenella</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994); Lange-Bertalot (2001): Sensitive
<i>Navicula digitoradiata</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994); Sabbe (1997)
<i>Navicula dilucida</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): freshwater or marine, epipelic. Ribeiro et al. (2013)
<i>Navicula erifuga</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Potapova (2009): <i>N. erifuga</i> prefers brackish water or fresh water of high mineral content, eutraphentic; Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Navicula cf. flagellifera</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Ribeiro et al. (2013); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Navicula gregaria</i> [morphotype 1]	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994); Ribeiro et al. (2013)
<i>Navicula gregaria</i> [morphotype 2]	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994); Ribeiro et al. (2013)
<i>Navicula lanceolata</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Navicula micradigitoradiata</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Lange-Bertalot (2001)
<i>Navicula pargemina</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Ribeiro et al. (2013)
<i>Navicula cf. pargemina</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Ribeiro et al. (2013)
<i>Navicula peregrina</i>	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994); Lange-Bertalot (2001)

Species	Salinity preferences	Habitat	Growth-form	References on Ecology
<i>Navicula perminuta</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994); Lange-Bertalot (2001)
<i>Navicula cf. perminuta</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994); Lange-Bertalot (2001)
<i>Navicula phyllepta</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994); Lange-Bertalot (2001)
<i>Navicula cf. phyllepta</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994); Lange-Bertalot (2001)
<i>Navicula cf. salinarum</i>	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994); Sabbe (1997)
<i>Navicula salinicola</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994); Sabbe (1997)
<i>Navicula cf. salinicola</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994); Sabbe (1997)
<i>Navicula slesviensis</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994); Lange-Bertalot (2001)
<i>Navicula spartinetensis</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Ribeiro et al. (2013)
<i>Navicula cf. starmachiooides</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Van Dam et al. (1994); Sabbe (1997)
<i>Navicula tripunctata</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994); Lange-Bertalot (2001); eutrophic waters with average to high electrolyte content
<i>Navicula cf. utlandshoerimensis</i>	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); freshwater or marine, epipelic. Witkowski et al. (2000)
<i>Navicula veneta</i>	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994); Lange-Bertalot (2001); very pollution tolerant. Electrolyte-rich to brackish waters
<i>Navicula viminooides</i> subsp. <i>cosmomarina</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipsammic	Round et al. (1990); freshwater or marine, epipelic. Ribeiro et al. (2013)
<i>Navicula wiesneri</i>	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Van Dam et al. (1994); Lange-Bertalot (2001)
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 1	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); freshwater or marine, epipelic
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 2	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); freshwater or marine, epipelic
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 3	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); freshwater or marine, epipelic
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 4	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); freshwater or marine, epipelic
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 5	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); freshwater or marine, epipelic
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 6	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); freshwater or marine, epipelic
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 7	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); freshwater or marine, epipelic
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 8	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); freshwater or marine, epipelic
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 9	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); freshwater or marine, epipelic
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 10	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); freshwater or marine, epipelic
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 11	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); freshwater or marine, epipelic
<i>Navicula</i> s.l. sp. 1	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); freshwater or marine, epipelic
<i>Navicula</i> s.l. sp. 2	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); freshwater or marine, epipelic
<i>Navicula</i> s.l. sp. 3	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); freshwater or marine, epipelic
<i>Nitzschia acicularis</i>	freshwater	benthos	epipelic	Van Dam et al. (1994); Kelly et al. (2005); Freshwater, tolerant to pollution

Species	Salinity preferences	Habitat	Growth-form	References on Ecology
<i>Nitzschia aequorea</i>	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): found in freshwaters, less common in brackish and marine sediments. Ribeiro et al. (2013)
<i>Nitzschia agnita</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Van Dam et al. (1994); Witkowski et al. (2000)
<i>Nitzschia amphibia</i>	fresh/terrestrial	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Nitzschia angularis</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Witkowski et al. (2000)
<i>Nitzschia brevissima</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Sabbe (1997)
<i>Nitzschia cf. capitellata</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Nitzschia cf. dissipata</i>	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994); Sabbe (1997)
<i>Nitzschia cf. distans</i>	marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991)
<i>Nitzschia dubia</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Nitzschia cf. dubia</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Nitzschia cf. filiformis</i>	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Nitzschia fonticola</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Nitzschia frustulum</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Nitzschia cf. gessneri</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Nitzschia incognita</i>	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); Krammer & Lange-Bertalot (1986-1992)
<i>Nitzschia lanceola</i> var. <i>minutula</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Van Dam et al. (1994); Witkowski et al. (2000)
<i>Nitzschia lorenziana</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); Witkowski et al. (2000)
<i>Nitzschia maxima</i>	marine	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994); Witkowski et al. (2000)
<i>Nitzschia microcephala</i>	freshwater	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); Kelly et al. (2005): Benthic in freshwaters of high ionic content
<i>Nitzschia nana</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Van Dam et al. (1994); Witkowski et al. (2000)
<i>Nitzschia ovalis</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994); Witkowski et al. (2000)
<i>Nitzschia palea</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994); Kelly et al. (2005): Benthic in freshwaters
<i>Nitzschia cf. parvula</i>	freshwater	benthos	epipelic	Van Dam et al. (1994) Kelly et al. (2005)
<i>Nitzschia pellucida</i>	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); Sabbe (1997)
<i>Nitzschia cf. pseudofonticola</i>	freshwater	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); Kelly et al. (2005)
<i>Nitzschia cf. pusilla</i>	freshwater	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); Kelly et al. (2005)
<i>Nitzschia recta</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Nitzschia rhopaloides</i>	marine	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); Witkowski et al. (2000)
<i>Nitzschia aff. inconspicua</i>	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Nitzschia sigma</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)

Species	Salinity preferences	Habitat	Growth-form	References on Ecology
<i>Nitzschia supralittorea</i>	freshwater	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994); Krammer & Lange-Bertalot (1986-1992)
<i>Nitzschia thermaloides</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); Witkowski et al. (2000)
<i>Nitzschia tubicola</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Nitzschia</i> sp. 1	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): large epipelic genus found in freshwaters, less common in brackish and marine sediments
<i>Nitzschia</i> sp. 2	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): large epipelic genus found in freshwaters, less common in brackish and marine sediments
<i>Nitzschia</i> sp. 3	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): large epipelic genus found in freshwaters, less common in brackish and marine sediments
<i>Nitzschia</i> sp. 4	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): large epipelic genus found in freshwaters, less common in brackish and marine sediments
<i>Nitzschia</i> sp. 5	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): large epipelic genus found in freshwaters, less common in brackish and marine sediments
<i>Nitzschia</i> sp. 6	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): large epipelic genus found in freshwaters, less common in brackish and marine sediments
<i>Nitzschia</i> sp. 7	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): large epipelic genus found in freshwaters, less common in brackish and marine sediments
<i>Nitzschia</i> sp. 8	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): large epipelic genus found in freshwaters, less common in brackish and marine sediments
<i>Nupella</i> sp. 1	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Lange-Bertalot et al. (2017)
<i>Odontella rostrata</i>	brackish/marine	thycoplankton	tychoplanktonic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Opephora horstiana</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	haptobenthic	Ribeiro et al. (2013); Witkowski et al. (2000)
<i>Opephora mutabilis</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994); Witkowski et al. (2000)
<i>Paralia cf. fenestrata</i>	brackish/marine	thycoplankton	tychoplanktonic	Round et al. (1990): found in marine inshore plankton but probably belonging on sandy sediments
<i>Paralia sulcata</i>	brackish/marine	thycoplankton	tychoplanktonic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Petrodictyon gemma</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Pinnularia divergentissima</i>	freshwater	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Pinnularia</i> sp. 1	freshwater	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): large epipelic genus; freshwater to (rarely) marine
<i>Pinnularia</i> sp. 2	freshwater	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): large epipelic genus; freshwater to (rarely) marine
<i>Plagiogrammopsis crawfordii</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipsammic	Round et al. (1990); Witkowski et al. (2000)
<i>Plagiogrammopsis minima</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipsammic	Round et al. (1990); Denys (1991); Sabbe et al. (2010)
<i>Plagiogrammopsis vanheurckii</i>	brackish/marine	thycoplankton	tychoplanktonic	Round et al. (1990); Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994); Sabbe (1997)
<i>Plagiolemma confusum</i>	marine	benthos	epipelic	Paddock (1988). Hendey (1964): Probably belongs to the subtropical flora
<i>Plagiotropis seriata</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): Brackish or marine, epipelic
<i>Planothidium delicatulum</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Planothidium frequentissimum</i>	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Lange-Bertalot et al. (2017); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Plagiotropis cf. vanheurckii</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): Brackish or marine, epipelic
<i>Planothidium hauckianum</i>	brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Lange-Bertalot et al. (2017); Van Dam et al. (1994); Witkowski et al. (2000)

Species	Salinity preferences	Habitat	Growth-form	References on Ecology
<i>Planothidium lanceolatum</i>	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Lange-Bertalot et al. (2017); Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Planothidium cf. lemmermannii</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Ribeiro et al. (2013)
<i>Planothidium cf. polaris</i>	marine	benthos	haptobenthic	Witkowski et al. (2000)
<i>Planothidium</i> sp. 1	fresh/brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Round et L.Bukhtiyarova (1996)
<i>Planothidium</i> sp. 2	fresh/brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Round et L.Bukhtiyarova (1996)
<i>Pleurosigma angulatum</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994); Hendey (1964)
<i>Pleurosigma inflatum</i>	marine	benthos	epipelic	Hendey (1964)
<i>Pleurosigma cf. salinarum</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Van Dam et al. (1994). Krammer & Lange-Bertalot (1986)
<i>Pleurosira laevis</i>	brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Round et al. (1990): ideal niche in brackish waters
<i>Podosira stelligera</i>	brackish/marine	thycoplankton	tychoplanktonic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Prestauroneis protractoides</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	AlgaeBase (2019). Liu et al (2015)
<i>Psammodyctyon mediterraneum</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Romagnoli et al (2014); Round et al. (1990)
<i>Psammodyctyon panduriforme</i> var. <i>continuum</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); Snoeijs & Balashova (1998)
<i>Psammodyctyon</i> sp. 1	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): marine, epipelic genus, particularly widespread on sandy substrata
<i>Psammodiscus nitidus</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipsammic	Denys (1991); Round et al (1990): attaches to sand grains in the marine inter- and subtidal
<i>Pseudofallacia tenera</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Ribeiro et al. (2013); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Pseudostaurosira brevisiriata</i>	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Pseudostaurosira parasitica</i>	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Pseudostaurosira parasitica</i> var. <i>subconstricta</i>	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Reimeria sinuata</i>	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Scolloneis tumida</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Sellaphora atomoides</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): freshwater and extending into brackish and probably into marine sites; epipelic
<i>Sellaphora nigri</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); Wetzel et al. (2015)
<i>Sellaphora cf. pseudopupula</i>	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Lange-Bertalot et al. (2017); Round et al. (1990)
<i>Sellaphora pupula</i>	freshwater	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); Kelly et al. (2005)
<i>Sellaphora cf. saugeresii</i>	freshwater	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); Wetzel et al. (2015)
<i>Sellaphora</i> sp. 1	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990): freshwater and extending into brackish and probably into marine sites; epipelic
<i>Rhaphoneis amphiceros</i>	marine	thycoplankton	tychoplanktonic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990): epipsammic; Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Simonsenia</i> sp. 1	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Witkowski et al. (2015)

Species	Salinity preferences	Habitat	Growth-form	References on Ecology
<i>Skeletonema</i> spp.	brackish/marine	plankton	planktonic	Round et al. (1990); coastal marine plankton
<i>Stauroforma</i> cf. <i>exiguiformis</i>	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Stauroneis</i> cf. <i>kriegeri</i>	fresh/terrestrial	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Stauroneis</i> cf. <i>marina</i>	fresh/terrestrial	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); Witkowski et al. (2000)
<i>Stauroneis</i> sp. 1	fresh/terrestrial	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); freshwater epipelic genus with some subaerial forms in soil and moss
<i>Staurophora amphioxys</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); Witkowski et al. (2000)
<i>Staurophora salina</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); Witkowski et al. (2000)
<i>Staurosira construens</i>	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Staurosira construens</i> var. <i>binodis</i>	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Staurosira construens</i> f. <i>subsalina</i>	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Lange-Bertalot et al. (2017); Round et al. (1990)
<i>Staurosira construens</i> var. <i>venter</i>	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Staurosirella martyi</i>	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Staurosirella oldenburgiana</i>	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Lange-Bertalot et al. (2017); Round et al. (1990)
<i>Staurosirella</i> cf. <i>pinnata</i>	freshwater	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Stephanodiscus hantzschii</i>	freshwater	plankton	planktonic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Stephanodiscus hantzschii</i> f. <i>tenuis</i>	fresh/brackish	plankton	planktonic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Stephanodiscus parvus</i>	freshwater	plankton	planktonic	Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Suriirella brebissonii</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Suriirella curvifacies</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); Ribeiro et al. (2013)
<i>Suriirella fastuosa</i>	marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Witkowski et al. (2000)
<i>Suriirella</i> cf. <i>turgida</i>	freshwater	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Suriirella</i> sp. 1	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); freshwater to marine. Epipelic
<i>Suriirella</i> sp. 2	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); freshwater to marine. Epipelic
<i>Suriirella</i> sp. 3	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); freshwater to marine. Epipelic
<i>Suriirella</i> sp. 4	brackish	benthos	epipelic	Round et al. (1990); freshwater to marine. Epipelic
<i>Tabularia fasciculata</i>	brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994); Kelly et al. (2005)
<i>Tabularia investiens</i>	brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Bérard-Therriault et al. (1999)
<i>Tabularia tabulata</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	haptobenthic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994); Snoeijis (1993)
<i>Suriirella atomus</i>	brackish/marine	benthos	epipelic	Denys (1991); Ribeiro et al. (2010)
<i>Thalassiosira lucens</i>	brackish/marine	thycoplankton	tychoplanktonic	Ribeiro et al. (2013); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Thalassiosira nitzschoides</i>	brackish	plankton	planktonic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)

Species	Salinity preferences	Habitat	Growth-form	References on Ecology
<i>Thalassiosira cf. angulata</i>	brackish/marine	plankton	planktonic	Muylaert & Sabbe (1996)
<i>Thalassiosira eccentrica</i>	brackish/marine	plankton	planktonic	Muylaert & Sabbe (1996); Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Thalassiosira lacustris</i>	fresh/brackish	plankton	planktonic	Round et al. (1990); Germain (1981)
<i>Thalassiosira mediterranea</i>	marine	plankton	planktonic	Round et al. (1990); Hasle & Syvertsen (1997)
<i>Thalassiosira minima</i>	brackish/marine	plankton	planktonic	Muylaert & Sabbe (1996)
<i>Thalassiosira proschkiniae</i>	brackish	tychoplankton	tychoplanktonic	Muylaert & Sabbe (1996)
<i>Thalassiosira punctigera</i>	brackish	plankton	planktonic	Muylaert & Sabbe (1996)
<i>Thalassiosira cf. simplex</i>	brackish	plankton	planktonic	Round et al. (1990); Sabbe (1997)
<i>Thalassiosira tealata</i>	marine	plankton	planktonic	AlgaeBase (2019)
<i>Thalassiosira tenera</i>	brackish/marine	plankton	planktonic	Sabbe (1997); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Thalassiosira</i> sp. 1	brackish	plankton	planktonic	Round et al. (1990); mainly in marine plankton
<i>Thalassiosira</i> sp. 2	brackish	plankton	planktonic	Round et al. (1990); mainly in marine plankton
<i>Thalassiosira</i> sp. 3	brackish	plankton	planktonic	Round et al. (1990); mainly in marine plankton
<i>Thalassiosira</i> sp. 4	brackish	plankton	planktonic	Round et al. (1990); mainly in marine plankton
<i>Thalassiosira</i> sp. 5	brackish/marine	tychoplankton	tychoplanktonic	Round et al. (1990); mainly in marine plankton
<i>Triceratium favius</i>	marine	tychoplankton	tychoplanktonic	Hendey (1964); Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990)
<i>Tryblionella apiculata</i>	brackish/marine	plankton	epipelagic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Tryblionella balatonis</i>	brackish/marine	plankton	epipelagic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990)
<i>Tryblionella calida</i>	brackish/marine	plankton	epipelagic	Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Tryblionella circumscuta</i>	brackish/marine	plankton	epipelagic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Tryblionella cf. debilis</i>	brackish	plankton	epipelagic	Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Tryblionella gracilis</i>	brackish/marine	plankton	epipelagic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Tryblionella hungarica</i>	brackish/marine	plankton	epipelagic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Tryblionella levidensis</i>	fresh/brackish	benthos	epipelagic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Tryblionella navicularis</i>	brackish/marine	plankton	epipelagic	Denys (1991); Round et al. (1990); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Tryblionella</i> sp. 1	brackish	plankton	epipelagic	Round et al. (1990); large epipelagic genus, widespread but not often common in brackish and marine sediments
<i>Ulnaria delicatissima</i>	freshwater	tychoplankton	tychoplanktonic	Krammer & Lange-Bertalot (1991); Van Dam et al. (1994)
<i>Zygoceros aff. atlanticus</i>	marine	tychoplankton	tychoplanktonic	Lavigne et al (2015)

Table 6: Occurrences. Diatom taxa found in the three sites per sampled station (1 to 5) and season (Spring and Autumn). Taxa listed with OMNIDIA codes (see Table 3).

OMNIDIA codes	DONGES					MEAN					BRILLANTES					
	Spring	Spring	Autumn	Spring	Autumn	Spring	Spring	Autumn	Spring	Spring	Spring	Spring	Autumn	Spring	Spring	Autumn
ADRU			X													
ADEG	X		X													
ADSA	X	X	X			X	X	X							X	X
ADSH	X															
ACHD sp1		X				X	X	X	X						X	
ACHD sp2			X													
ACHD sp3																
ACHD sp4																
ACHD sp5								X								
ADSP sp1								X								
ANMIN																
AOTE																X
ASEN		X	X					X								X
ACOP		X				X	X	X							X	X
AHLN						X		X								
AMID																X
AOVA		X	X			X		X								X
APED		X	X	X		X	X	X	X							X
ASAC																X
AVTU		X	X			X	X	X	X							X
ANTN																
AFOR			X	X												
AAMB	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X							X
AUBR																
AUGR	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X							X
AUIS	X	X	X													X
AUPU	X	X	X	X		X										
AUSU	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X							X
BBER				X		X	X	X	X							
BFEN						X	X	X	X							
BLUC																X
	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	

Stations

OMNIDIA codes	DONGES		MEAN		BRILLANTES	
	Spring	Autumn	Spring	Autumn	Spring	Autumn
BBRO	X	X	X		X	
CAEM	X				X	
CSHU	X					
CWES						X
CADH			X			
CVLP				X		
CRSM	X	X				
CLFA				X		
CDIS			X			X
CLNT	X	X	X	X	X	X
CPED	X	X	X	X		
CNTH	X	X	X	X		
CSCU	X	X				
CSTF	X					
COCO sp1	X					
CICO		X				X
CSNU	X	X	X		X	
CTPL			X		X	
CINV	X	X	X	X	X	X
CAGR	X	X	X	X	X	X
CCHO			X	X	X	
CMED	X	X	X	X	X	X
CMEN	X	X	X	X	X	X
CYCL sp1					X	
CYCL sp2					X	
CCLO		X	X	X	X	X
CYGR	X	X	X	X	X	X
CELL	X				X	
CSOL	X					
CBEL	X	X	X	X	X	X
CTUM						
CYMB sp1					X	
CYMB sp2		X				
	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5

Stations

OMNIDIA codes	DONGES		MEAN		BRILLANTES	
	Spring	Autumn	Spring	Autumn	Spring	Autumn
CBAM						
DELM	X X X	X X X X	X X X X	X X X X	X X	X X
DSRL						
DSUB				X		X
DCOF	X X X X	X	X	X		
DAES				X		
DSMI		X				
DVAC					X	
DVET						
DWEI					X	
DIPL-sp1						X
DPST	X X X X	X X X X	X X X X	X X X X	X X X X	X X X X
DSTT	X X X	X	X X X X	X	X X X X	X X X X
DWOL	X X X X	X	X X X X		X	X X X
ENCY sp1	X		X		X	
EALA				X		
EPAL				X		X
EOLI sp1	X X X		X			
EADN	X					
EMIN						
EUNO sp1	X					
EUDU	X	X X X X	X	X X X X	X X X X	X X X X
FAMP						
FHEL	X					
FMPU			X			
FANY	X X					
FPYG			X			
FSCL		X				
FWUE						
FALL-sp1		X				X
FIMP		X	X			X
FCAP			X X X X			
FTNA		X				
	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5

Stations

OMNIDIA codes	DONGES					MEAN					BRILLANTES																
	Spring					Autumn					Spring					Autumn											
	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5		
HUCO																											
KAAM																											
KCLE																											
LCMT																											
LUND																											
LFRQ																											
LGOE																											
MBAL																											
MDAN																											
MAAT																											
MAEX																											
MEMI																											
MLIN																											
MNUM																											
KCLE																											
LCMT																											
LUND																											
LFRQ																											
LGOE																											
MBAL																											
MDAN																											
MAAT																											
MAEX																											
MPMI																											
MEMI																											
MLIN																											
MNUM																											
MVAR																											
MELO sp1																											
MCIR																											
NABS																											
NALK																											
NANT																											

OMNIDIA codes	DONGES		MEAN		BRILLANTES	
	Spring	Autumn	Spring	Autumn	Spring	Autumn
NARE	X	X			X	
NBIP		X				X
NBOZ						
NCIN		X		X		
NCTE	X					
NDIG					X	
NDLD		X				
NERI				X		
NFGF						
NGRE m1	X	X	X	X	X	X
NGRE m2		X		X		
NLAN	X				X	
NMDG	X	X	X	X	X	X
NPGN	X	X	X	X	X	X
NPGN	X	X	X	X		
NPRG						
NPNU		X			X	X
NPNU	X			X		
NPHY						
NPHY	X	X	X	X	X	X
NSAL	X				X	
NSLC		X		X		
NSLC	X	X	X	X	X	X
NSLE		X				
NXSP	X	X	X	X	X	X
NSTA				X		
NTPT						
NUTL		X				
NVEN			X			
NVMC nw				X		
NWIE		X		X		X
NAVI sp1					X	
NAVI sp2			X			
	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5

Stations

OMNIDIA codes	DONGES		MEAN		BRILLANTES	
	Spring	Autumn	Spring	Autumn	Spring	Autumn
NAVI sp3						X
NAVI sp4		X X				X X X X
NAVI sp5		X				
NAVI sp6		X				X
NAVI sp7		X X		X		
NAVI sp8		X		X		
NAVI sp9				X		
NAVI sp10				X		
NAVI sp11		X				
NAVI si sp1		X		X		
NAVI si sp2				X X X X		X X X X
NAVI si sp3		X				
NACI	X X		X X		X	
NEQO	X X X X	X X X X	X X X X X X	X X X X	X X X X	X X X X
NAGN				X X		
NAMP	X X X X	X		X X X X	X X X X	
NIAG	X X X					
NBRE	X					X
NCPL				X		X X X X
NDIS	X X X X	X		X X X X	X X X X X X	X X X X
NIDS				X X X X	X X X X X X	
NDUB				X		
NDUB					X	
NFIL					X	
NFON	X X X X	X X			X	
NIFR	X X X X X X	X X X X	X X X X X X	X X X X	X X X X	X X X X
NGES						
NICN						
NINC						
NLMN						X
NLOR				X		X X
NMAX						X X X X
NMIC					X	X X X X
	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5

Stations

OMNIDIA codes	DONGES		MEAN		BRILLANTES	
	Spring	Autumn	Spring	Autumn	Spring	Autumn
NNAN						X
NOVA						
NPAL	X X X X		X	X X X X		
NPAR	X X		X X X X X	X X X X	X X X X	
NIPE			X			
NPSF	X		X		X X	
NIPU	X	X X	X	X X	X X X X	X X X X
NIRH		X				
NSIG	X X X		X X X X	X X X X	X X X X	
NZSU		X X X X				
NTHE		X X X	X	X X X		X X X
NTUB	X X X X		X X	X X X	X X X	
NITZ sp1	X X X					
NITZ sp2		X	X	X X X		X
NITZ sp3		X	X X	X X X X		X
NITZ sp4		X		X X X X X		X
NITZ sp6						
NITZ sp7						
NITZ sp8		X			X	X X X X
NITZ sp9		X X X X		X X X		X X X X
NUPE sp1		X				
OHOR			X			
OMUT		X		X X X X	X X X X	
PFEN	X X X X	X X X X	X X X X	X X X X	X X X X	X X
PSUL	X X X X	X X X X	X X X X	X X X X X	X X X X X	X X X X
PGEM		X	X	X X		X
PDVG			X			
PINU sp1			X			X
PINU sp2		X				
PGGC						X
PGMI	X X X	X X X X	X X X X	X X X X X	X X X X	X X X X
PLGV	X X X	X X X X	X X X X	X X X X X	X X X X	X X X X
PLCF nw	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5

Stations

OMNIDIA codes	DONGES		MEAN		BRILLANTES	
	Spring	Autumn	Spring	Autumn	Spring	Autumn
PTSR nw		X		X		X
PVHK		X X X	X	X	X X X	X X X
PTDE	X	X	X X X X		X	X
PTHA	X X	X	X	X X		
PTLA	X X X X	X X X X	X		X X	X
PLEM	X		X		X	
PTPO		X				
PLTD sp1		X				
PLTD sp2				X		
PANG	X		X X X	X		X
PIFT			X			
PSAL		X X		X X X X	X X X	X X X
PLEV	X	X				
POST	X X X X	X X X		X X X X	X X	X X X
PPRD	X					
PSMM nw	X		X			
PPFC	X X X X	X X X		X X X X	X X X	X
PSDT sp1					X	
PNIT	X					
PFTN			X X X	X		X
PSBR				X X		
PPRS					X	
PPSC						
RSIN		X				
RAMP	X X X X	X X X X	X X X	X X X X	X X X X	X X X
STUM					X X	
SEAT		X	X			
SNIG	X X X	X X X	X X X X	X X	X X	X
SPPU						
SPUP	X X					
SSGE	X X X X	X X X	X		X X X X	X
SELL sp1						
SIMO sp1	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5

Stations

OMNIDIA codes	DONGES					MEAN					BRILLANTES									
	Spring		Autumn			Spring		Autumn			Spring		Autumn							
	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
SKSP	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
SEXG																				
STKR																				
STMA																				
STAU sp1																				
SAXY																				
SPHS			X	X		X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X
SCON	X					X					X									
SCBI																				
SCSL																				
SCVE	X			X	X	X	X	X	X		X									
SLMA																				
SOLD																				
SPIN																				
SHAN	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X
SHTE	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X
SPAV																				
SATO																				
SBRE	X	X									X	X	X							
SCUR																				
SFAS																				
STUR																				
SURI sp1	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X
SURI sp2																				
SURI sp3																				
SURI sp4																				
TFAS																				
TINV																				
TTAB																				
TLUC																				
THNI																				
THAG	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X
TBAL	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5

Stations

OMNIDIA codes	DONGES		MEAN		BRILLANTES					
	Spring	Autumn	Spring	Autumn	Spring	Autumn				
TTEA nw	X	X	X	X	X	X				
TDEC	X	X	X	X	X	X				
THEC	X	X	X	X	X	X				
THLA										
TMED	X	X	X	X	X	X				
TMIN			X	X	X	X				
TPRK			X	X	X	X				
TPUN	X	X								
THLS nw	X		X	X	X	X				
TTEN										
THAL-sp1	X									
THAL-sp2	X	X		X						
THAL-sp3										
THAL-sp4		X								
THAL-sp5		X								
TFAV										
TAPI	X	X	X	X	X	X				
TRBA	X									
TCAL	X	X		X	X	X				
TCIR						X				
TDEB		X								
TGRL				X	X	X				
THUN		X								
TNAV										
TRYB sp1				X						
UDEL	X									
ZATL				X						
	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5

Stations

5. References

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6. Plates

All micrographs were taken with a LEICA ICC50W 5-megapixel camera mounted on a Leica DM2500 LED microscope, equipped with a Brightfield and Differential Interference Contrast (DIC) and using a Leica HC PL Fluotar 100x oil objective (numerical aperture 1.32). The magnification of the micrographs in the atlas is x2000, unless otherwise indicated. This allows a more direct comparison between taxa of different sizes. This magnification means that, in the plates, 1 cm corresponds to 5 μm of actual object size.

The identification of diatoms was carried out according to the following works: Peragallo and Peragallo (1897-1908), Hendey (1964); Germain (1981), Krammer and Lange-Bertalot (1986, 1988, 1991a, 1991b), Round et al. (1990), Snoeijs (1993), Snoeijs and Vilbaste (1994), Snoeijs and Potopova (1995), Snoeijs and Kasperoviciene (1996), Snoeijs and Balashova (1998), Hasle and Syvertsen (1997), Witkowski et al. (2000), Lange-Bertalot, 2001 (2001), Krammer and Lange-Bertalot (2002), Krammer and Lange-Bertalot, (2003); Levkov (2009), Ector et al. (2015), Lange-Bertalot et al (2017), as well as, the doctoral theses by Kuylenstierna (1989-1990), Rincé (1993), Sabbe (1997) and Ribeiro (2010).

The arrangement and placement of the different taxa in the 42 plates of this atlas tries to follow the classification system proposed by Round et al. (1990). Even though it is outdated, it is a conventional and familiar classification to anyone that has worked with diatoms.

Plate 1

x2000

- 1 *Actinocyclus normanii* (W.Gregory ex Greville) Hustedt
- 2 *Actinocyclus octonarius* var. *tenellus* (Brébisson) Hendey
- 3 *Thalassiosira baltica* (Grunow) Ostenfeld (x1000)
- 4-6 *Skeletonema* spp. [connective view]
- 7-8 *Skeletonema* spp. [valve-view]

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Plate 2

1-2 *Podosira stelligera* (Bailey) A. Mann (x2000)

3-4 *Coscinodiscus jonesianus* (Greville) Ostenfeld (x1000)

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Plate 3

x2000

1 *Thalassiosira* sp. 4

2-3 *Thalassiosira eccentrica* (Ehrenberg) Cleve (x1000)

4-5 *Thalassiosira lacustris* (Grunow) Hasle

6 *Asteromphalus flabellatus* (Brébisson) Greville

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Plate 4

x2000

1-3 *Thalassiosira* cf. *angulata* (W.Gregory) Hasle

4-7 *Thalassiosira decipiens* (Grunow ex Van Heurck) E.G.Jørgensen

8 *Thalassiosira* cf. *simplex* Hustedt

9-10 *Thalassiosira tenera* Proschkina-Lavrenko

11-12 *Thalassiosira* sp. 1 [similar to *Thalassiosira kushirensis* H.Takano]

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Plate 5

x2000

- 1 *Thalassiosira minima* Gaarder
- 2-3 *Thalassiosira* sp. 5
- 4-5 *Thalassiosira tealata* Takano
- 6-7 *Thalassiosira proschkinae* Makarova
- 8-11 *Thalassiosira mediterranea* (Schröder) Hasle
- 12-14 *Thalassiosira* sp. 2
- 15-16 *Thalassiosira* sp. 3
- 17-18 *Thalassiosira punctigera* (Castracane) Hasle (x1000)
- 19 *Thalassiocyclus lucens* (Hustedt) Håkansson & Mahood

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Plate 6

x2000

- 1 *Cyclotella* sp. 1
- 2 *Cyclotella meneghiniana* Kützing
- 3-4 *Cyclotella* cf. *choctawhatcheeana* Prasad
- 5-6 *Cyclotella* cf. *meduanae* H.Germain
- 7 *Cyclotella* sp. 2
- 8-9 *Cyclotella* cf. *atomus* var. *gracilis* Gental & Kiss
- 10-11 *Discostella stelligera* var. *tenuis* (Hustedt) Houk & Klee
- 12 *Discostella* cf. *woltereckii* (Hustedt) Houk & Klee
- 13-15 *Discostella pseudostelligera* (Hustedt) Houk & Klee
- 16-18 *Stephanodiscus hantzschii* Grunow
- 19-21 *Stephanodiscus hantzschii* f. *tenuis* (Hustedt) Håkansson & Stoermer
- 22-23 *Stephanodiscus parvus* Stoermer & Håkansson
- 24-26 *Cyclostephanos invisitatus* (M.H.Hohn & Hellermann) E.C.Theriot,
Stoermer & Håkansson
- 27-28 *Lindavia comta* (Kützing) Nakov, Gullory, Julius, Theriot & Alverson

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Plate 7

x2000

1-3 *Paralia* cf. *fenestrata* Sawai & Nagumo

4-5 *Paralia* *sulcata* (Ehrenberg) Cleve

6-7 *Actinoptychus* *senarius* (Ehrenberg) Ehrenberg (x1000)

8 *Triceratium* *favus* Ehrenberg (x1000) [Fragment]

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Plate 8

x2000

1-2 *Melosira* sp. 1

3-4 *Melosira nummuloides* C.Agardh

5-6 *Melosira varians* C.Agardh

7-9 *Melosira lineata* (Dillwyn) C.Agardh

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Plate 9

x2000

1-6 *Melosira moniliformis* (O.F.Müller) C.Agardh

7-13 *Chaetoceros* spp. [Hypnospore]

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Plate 10

x1000

1-3 *Zygodontia cf. atlanticus* (Frenguelli) Sar

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Plate 11

x2000

1-2 *Aulacoseira ambigua* (Grunow) Simonsen

3-5 *Aulacoseira brasiliensis* P.I.Tremarin, L.Carvalho Torgan & T.A.Veiga Ludwig

6-9 *Aulacoseira pusilla* (F.Meister) A.Tuji & A.Houk

10-12 *Aulacoseira islandica* (O. Müller) Simonsen

13-14 *Aulacoseira granulata* (Ehrenberg) Simonsen

15-17 *Aulacoseira subartica* (O. Müller) Haworth

18 *Odontella rostrata* (Hustedt) Simonsen [connective view]

19-20 *Odontella rostrata* (Hustedt) Simonsen

21 *Cerataulus smithii* Ralfs [valve view]

Plate 12

x2000

1-2 *Lithodesmium undulatum* Ehrenberg (x1000)

3-4 *Pleurosira laevis* (Ehrenberg) Compère (x1000)

5 *Brockmanniella brockmannii* (Hustedt) Hasle, Stosch & Syvertsen

6 *Cymatosira belgica* Grunow

7 *Plagiogrammopsis crawfordii* Witkowski

8-10 *Plagiogrammopsis vanheurckii* (Grunow) Hasle, Stosch & Syvertsen

11 *Plagiogrammopsis minima* (Salah) Sabbe & Witkowski

12-13 *Eunotogramma* cf. *dubium* Hustedt

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Plate 13

x2000

- 1-2 *Fragilaria* cf. *improbula* Witkowski & Lange-Bertalot
- 3-4 *Gedaniella flavovirens* (H.Takano) Chunlian Li, A.Witkowski & M.P.Ashworth
- 5 *Pseudostaurosira brevistriata* (Grunow) D.M.Williams & Round
- 6-7 *Opephora mutabilis* (Grunow) Sabbe & Wyverman
- 8 *Opephora horstiana* Witkowski
- 9 *Fragilaria* s.l. sp. 1
- 10-12 *Fragilaria* s.l. sp. 2
- 13-14 *Fragilaria* s.l. sp. 3
- 15-17 *Fragilaria* s.l. sp. 4
- 18 *Fragilaria* s.l. sp. 5
- 19-20 *Fragilaria* cf. *capucina* Desmazières
- 21-22 *Staurosira construens* Ehrenberg
- 23 *Staurosira construens* var. *venter* (Ehrenberg) P.B.Hamilton
- 24 *Staurosira construens* f. *subsalina* (Hustedt) Bukhtiyarova
- 25 *Staurosira construens* var. *binodis* (Ehrenberg) P.B.Hamilton
- 26 *Staurosirella oldenburgiana* (Hustedt) Morales
- 27 *Staurosirella martyi* (Héribaud-Joseph) E.A.Morales & K.M.Manoylov
- 28-30 *Staurosirella pinnata* (Ehrenberg) D.M.Williams & Round
- 31 *Pseudostaurosira parasitica* (W.Smith) E.Morales
- 32 *Pseudostaurosira parasitica* var. *subconstricta* (Grunow) E.Morales
- 33 *Stauroforma* cf. *exiguiformis* (Lange-Bertalot) Flower, Jones & Round
- 34 *Tabularia investiens* (W.Smith) D.M.Williams & Round
- 35-36 *Belonastrum berlinense* (Lemmermann) Round & Maidana

Plate 14

x2000

- 1-2 *Ctenophora pulchella* var. *lanceolata* (O'Meara) L.Bukhtiyarova
- 3 *Tabularia fasciculata* (C.Agardh) D.M.Williams & Round
- 4 *Tabularia tabulata* (C.Agardh) Snoeijs
- 5 *Thalassionema nitzschioides* (Grunow) Mereschkowsky
- 6 *Asterionella formosa* Hassall
- 7 *Fragilaria tenera* var. *nanana* (Lange-Bertalot) Lange-Bertalot & S.Ulrich
- 8 *Ulnaria delicatissima* (W.Smith) Aboal & P.C.Silva
- 9-10 *Mastogloia* cf. *danseyi* (Thwaites) Thwaites ex W.Smith
- 11 *Mastogloia baltica* Grunow
- 12 *Meridion circulare* (Greville) C.Agardh

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Plate 15

x2000

1 *Psammodiscus nitidus* (W.Gregory) Round & D.G.Mann

2-4 *Rhaphoneis ampiceros* (Ehrenberg) Ehrenberg

5 *Meloneis mimallis* I.Louvrou, D.B.Danielidis & A.Economou-Amilli

6-8 *Delphineis minutissima* (Hustedt) Simonsen

9 *Delphineis surirelloides* (Simonsen) G.W.Andrews

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Plate 16

x2000

- 1 *Encyonema* sp. 1
- 2 *Cymbopleura* cf. *amphicephala* (Nägeli) Krammer
- 3 *Cymbella* sp. 2
- 4 *Cymbella* sp. 1
- 5 *Cymbella tumida* (Brébisson) Van Heurck
- 6-7 *Staurophora* cf. *amphioxys* (W.Gregory) D.G.Mann
- 8-9 *Staurophora salina* (W.Smith) Mereschkowsky

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Plate 17

x2000

- 1 *Gomphonema* sp. 6
- 2 *Gomphonema* sp. 7
- 3-4 *Gomphonema* sp. 2
- 5-6 *Gomphonema* sp. 1
- 7 *Gomphonema* sp. 4
- 8 *Gomphonema* sp. 3
- 9 *Gomphonema* sp. 5
- 10 *Reimeria sinuata* (W.Gregory) Kociolek & Stoermer
- 11 *Anorthoneis* cf. *tenuis* Hustedt
- 12 *Cocconeis* sp.1
- 13-14 *Cocconeis* cf. *neothumensis* Krammer
- 15 *Cocconeis disculus* (Schumann) Cleve
- 16 *Cocconeis stauroneiformis* H.Okuno
- 17 *Cocconeis scutellum* Ehrenberg
- 18-21 *Cocconeis lineata* Ehrenberg
- 22 *Cocconeis placentula* var. *euglypta* (Ehrenberg) Grunow
- 23-25 *Cocconeis pediculus* Ehrenberg

Plate 18

x2000

- 1-10 *Achnantheridium* sp. 1
- 11-12 *Achnantheridium* sp. 3
- 13 *Achnantheridium* sp. 4
- 14 *Achnantheridium* sp. 5
- 15 *Achnantheridium* sp. 2
- 16-17 *Achnantheridium* cf. *subhudsonis* (Hustedt) H.Kobayasi
- 18-19 *Achnantheridium* cf. *saprophilum* (H.Kobayashi & Mayama) Round & Bukhtiyarova
- 20-21 *Achnantheridium* cf. *druartii* Rimet & Couté
- 22-23 *Achnantheridium exiguum* (Grunow) Czarnecki
- 24-26 *Planotheridium lanceolatum* (Brébisson ex Kützing) Lange-Bertalot
- 27 *Planotheridium frequentissimum* (Lange-Bertalot) Lange-Bertalot
- 28 *Planotheridium* sp. 1
- 29 *Planotheridium* cf. *lemmermannii* (Hustedt) E.A.Morales
- 30 *Planotheridium* cf. *polaris* (Østrup) Witkowski
- 31-32 *Planotheridium hauckianum* (Grunow) Bukhtiyarova
- 33 *Planotheridium* sp. 2
- 34-38 *Planotheridium delicatulum* (Kützing) Round & Bukhtiyarova
- 39-41 *Karayevia amoena* (Hustedt) Bukhtiyarova
- 42-44 *Karayevia clevei* (Grunow) Round & Bukhtiyarova
- 45 *Diploneis vetula* (A.W.F.Schmidt) Cleve

Plate 19

x2000

- 1 *Pinnularia* sp. 1
- 2 *Pinnularia* sp. 2 (x1000)
- 3 *Pinnularia divergentissima* (Grunow) Cleve
- 4 *Caloneis aemula* (A.Schmidt) Cleve
- 5 *Caloneis schumanniana* (Grunow) Cleve
- 6 *Caloneis westii* (W.Smith) Hendey
- 7-8 *Diploneis weissflogii* (A.W.F.Schmidt) Cleve

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Plate 20

x2000

- 1 *Diploneis schmidtii* Cleve
- 2 *Diploneis* cf. *vacilans* (A.Schmidt) Cleve
- 3 *Diploneis aestuarii* Hustedt
- 4 *Diploneis* sp. 1
- 5 *Luticola frequentissima* Levkov, Metzeltin & A.Pavlov
- 6-7 *Luticola goeppertiana* (Bleisch) D.G.Mann ex J.Rarick, S.Wu,
S.S.Lee & Edlund
- 8 *Berkeleya fennica* Juhlin-Dannfelt
- 9 *Cavinula* cf. *lapidosa* (Krasske) Lange-Bertalot
- 10 *Plagiolemma confusum* (Hendey) Paddock
- 11 *Scolioneis tumida* (Brébisson ex Kützing) D.G.Mann (x1000)
- 12 *Frustulia interposita* (Lewis) De Toni (x1000)
- 13 *Diadesmis confervacea* Kützing
- 14 *Humidophila contenta* (Grunow) Lowe, Kociolek, Johansen, Van de Vijver,
Lange-Bertalot & Kopalová
- 15 *Biremis lucens* (Hustedt) K.Sabbe, A.Witkowski & W.Vyverman
- 16 *Anomoeoneis sphaerophora* Pfitzer

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Plate 21

x1000

1 *Climaconeis fasciculata* (Grunow ex Cleve) E.J.Cox

2-3 *Plagiotropis seriata* (Cleve) Kuntze

4-5 *Plagiotropis* cf. *vanheurckii* Grunow (x2000)

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Plate 22

x2000

1-3 *Navicula spartinetensis* Sullivan & Reimer

4 *Navicula* sp. 8

5-7 *Navicula erifuga* Lange-Bertalot

8 *Navicula* cf. *cryptotenella* Lange-Bertalot

9 *Navicula dilucida* Hustedt

10-11 *Navicula* sp. 4

12 *Navicula* sp. 5

13-14 *Navicula wiesneri* Lange-Bertalot

15-16 *Navicula* cf. *abscondita* Hustedt

17 *Navicula* sp. 1

18-19 *Navicula* cf. *salinarum* Grunow

20-21 *Navicula microdigitoradiata* Lange-Bertalot

22-23 *Navicula bipustulata* Mann

24-25 *Navicula* sp. 7

26 *Navicula* sp. 6

Plate 23

x2000

- 1-3 *Navicula* cf. *flagellifera* Hustedt
- 4 *Navicula gregaria* Donkin [morphotype 1]
- 5 *Navicula gregaria* Donkin [morphotype 2]
- 6 *Navicula* sp. 9
- 7 *Navicula veneta* Kützing
- 8 *Navicula* sl. sp. 3
- 9 *Navicula phyllepta* Kützing
- 10-12 *Navicula* cf. *phyllepta* Kützing [morphotype 2]
- 13 *Navicula* cf. *phyllepta* Kützing [morphotype 1]
- 14 *Navicula* sl. sp. 1
- 15-16 *Navicula aleksandrae* Lange-Bertalot, Bogaczewicz-Adamczak & Witkowski
- 17 *Navicula viminoides* subsp. *cosmomarina* Lange-Bertalot, Witkowski, Bogaczewicz-Adamczak & Zgrundo
- 18 *Navicula bozenae* Lange-Bertalot, Witkowski & Zgrundo
- 19-20 *Navicula* cf. *utlandshoerniensis* Van Landingham
- 21-22 *Navicula cincta* (Ehrenberg) Ralfs in Pritchard
- 23-26 *Navicula digitoradiata* (W.Gregory) Ralfs
- 27 *Navicula* cf. *antonii* Lange-Bertalot

Plate 24

x2000

1-2 *Navicula tripunctata* (O.F. Müller) Bory

3 *Navicula slesvicensis* Grunow

4-5 *Navicula lanceolata* (Agardh) Ehrenberg

6-7 *Navicula arenaria* Donkin

8 *Navicula peregrina* (Ehrenberg) Kützing

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Plate 25

x2000

- 1 *Stauroneis* cf. *marina* Hustedt
- 2 *Stauroneis* sp. 1
- 3 *Stauroneis* cf. *kriegeri* R.M.Patrick
- 4 *Prestauroneis protractoides* (Hustedt) Q.Liu & Kociolek
- 5-6 *Hippodonta hungarica* (Grunow) Lange-Bertalot, Metzeltin & Witkowski
- 7 *Hippodonta caotica* A. Witkowski, H. Lange-Bertalot & D. Metzeltin
- 8 *Hippodonta linearis* (Østrup) Lange-Bertalot, Metzeltin & Witkowski
- 9 *Geissleria decussis* (Østrup) Lange-Bertalot & Metzeltin
- 10-11 *Craticula subminuscula* (Manguin) C.E. Wetzel & Ector
- 12 *Eolimna* sp. 1
- 13 *Adlafia* sp1
- 14 *Nupella* sp. 1
- 15-16 *Mayamaea* cf. *excelsa* (Krasske) Lange-Bertalot
- 17-18 *Fistulifera saprophila* (Lange-Bertalot & Bonik) Lange-Bertalot
- 19 *Mayamaea atomus* (Kützing) Lange-Bertalot
- 20-23 *Navicula pargemina* G.J.C.Underwood & M.L.Yallop
- 24-25 *Navicula* cf. *pargemina* G.J.C.Underwood & M.L.Yallop
- 26 *Navicula* cf. *starmachioides* A.Witkowski & Lange-Bertalot
- 27-29 *Navicula perminuta* Grunow
- 30-31 *Navicula* cf. *perminuta* Grunow
- 32 *Navicula* sp. 2
- 33 *Navicula* sp. 3
- 34 *Navicula salinicola* Hustedt
- 35-38 *Navicula* cf. *salinicola* Hustedt
- 39 *Navicula* sp. 10
- 40 *Navicula* sp. 11
- 41-43 *Navicula* sl. sp. 2

Plate 26

x2000

- 1-2 *Fallacia* sp. 1
- 3 *Fallacia pygmaea* (Kützing) Stickle & D.G.Mann
- 4 *Fallacia helensis* (Schulz) D.G.Mann
- 5 *Fallacia* cf. *ny* (Cleve) D.G.Mann
- 6 *Fallacia scaldensis* K.Sabbe & K.Muylaert
- 7 *Fallacia amphipleuroides* (Hustedt) D.G.Mann
- 8 *Fallacia margino-punctata* K.Sabbe & W.Vyverman
- 9 *Fallacia* cf. *wuestii* (R.Simonsen) K.Sabbe & K.Muylaert
- 10-11 *Pseudofallacia tenera* (Hustedt) Y.Liu, Kociolek & Q.Wang
- 12 *Sellaphora pupula* (Kützing) Mereschkovsky
- 13-15 *Sellaphora* cf. *saugerresii* (Desmazières) C.E.Wetzel & D.G.Mann
- 16-20 *Sellaphora nigri* (De Notaris) C.E.Wetzel & L. Ector
- 21 *Sellaphora* sp. 1
- 22 *Sellaphora* cf. *pseudopupula* (Krasske) Lange-Bertalot
- 23-24 *Sellaphora atomoides* (Grunow) Wetzel & Van de Vijver
- 25-27 *Gyrosigma limosum* Sterrenburg & Underwood (x1000)
- 28 *Gyrosigma wansbeckii* (Donkin) Cleve (x1000)

Plate 27

x1000

1-2 *Gyrosigma acuminatum* var. *gallicum* (Grunow) Cleve

3-4 *Gyrosigma attenuatum* (Kützing) Rabenhorst

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Plate 28

x1000

1-2 *Haslea nipkowii* (Meister) M.Poulin & G.Massé

3-4 *Gyrosigma fasciola* (Ehrenberg) J.W.Griffith & Henfrey

5 *Gyrosigma scalproides* (Rabenhorst) Cleve

6-7 *Gyrosigma eximium* (Thwaites) Boyer

8 *Gyrosigma balticum* (Ehrenberg) Rabenhorst (x500)

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Plate 29

x1000

- 1 *Pleurosigma angulatum* (J.T.Quekett) W.Smith (x500)
- 2-3 *Pleurosigma* cf. *salinarum* (Grunow) Grunow (x500)
- 4-5 *Pleurosigma inflatum* Shadbolt
- 6 *Gyrosigma macrum* (W.Smith) J.W.Griffith & Henfrey

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Plate 30

x2000

- 1 *Simonsenia* sp. 1
- 2 *Nitzschia* aff. *inconspicua* Grunow
- 3-6 *Nitzschia frustulum* (Kützing) Grunow in Cleve & Grunow
- 7-9 *Nitzschia tubicola* Grunow
- 10-11 *Nitzschia fonticola* (Grunow) Grunow
- 12-13 *Nitzschia* cf. *pusilla* Grunow
- 14 *Nitzschia* sp. 2
- 15 *Nitzschia* sp. 5
- 16 *Nitzschia* sp. 4
- 17 *Nitzschia microcephala* Grunow
- 18 *Nitzschia lanceola* var. *minutula* Grunow
- 19 *Nitzschia amphibia* Grunow
- 20 *Nitzschia ovalis* H.J. Arnott
- 21 *Nitzschia palea* (Kützing) W. Smith
- 22 *Nitzschia aequorea* Hustedt
- 23 *Nitzschia* sp. 3
- 24 *Nitzschia incognita* Legler & Krasske
- 25-26 *Nitzschia* cf. *distans* W.Gregory
- 27 *Nitzschia* cf. *capitellata* Hustedt
- 28 *Nitzschia* cf. *pseudofonticola* Hustedt
- 29 *Nitzschia agnita* Hustedt
- 30-32 *Nitzschia* cf. *dissipata* (Kützing) Rabenhorst

Plate 31

x2000

- 1 *Nitzschia supralitorea* Lange-Bertalot
- 2 *Nitzschia* cf. *parvula* W. Smith non Lewis
- 3-5 *Nitzschia thermaloides* Hustedt
- 6 *Nitzschia dubia* W. Smith
- 7 *Nitzschia brevissima* Grunow
- 8 *Nitzschia lorenziana* Grunow
- 9 *Nitzschia nana* Grunow
- 10 *Nitzschia pellucida* Grunow
- 11-12 *Denticula subtilis* Grunow
- 13 *Tryblionella* cf. *debilis* Arnott ex O'Meara
- 14 *Nitzschia* sp. 6
- 15 *Nitzschia* sp. 8
- 16 *Nitzschia rhopalodioides* Hustedt

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Plate 32

x1000

- 1 *Nitzschia* cf. *dubia* W.Smith (x500)
- 2-3 *Nitzschia* cf. *filiformis* (W.Smith) Van Heurck (x2000)
- 4 *Nitzschia* cf. *gessneri* Hustedt
- 5 *Nitzschia maxima* Grunow (x500)
- 6 *Nitzschia* sp. 1

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Plate 33

x2000

- 1 *Hantzschia amphioxys* (Ehrenberg) Grunow
- 2 *Nitzschia* sp. 7
- 3 *Nitzschia acicularis* (Kützing) W. Smith
- 4 *Nitzschia angularis* W. Smith
- 5 *Bacillaria paxillifera* (O.F.Müller) T. Marsson
- 6-7 *Tryblionella* sp. 1
- 8 *Psammodictyon* sp. 1
- 9-11 *Psammodictyon panduriforme* var. *continuum* (Grunow) Snoeijs
- 12 *Psammodictyon mediterraneum* (Hustedt) D.G. Mann
- 13-14 *Tryblionella balatonis* (Grunow) D.G. Mann
- 15 *Grunowia tabellaria* (Grunow) Rabenhorst

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Plate 34

x2000

1 *Nitzschia recta* Hantzsch ex Rabenhorst

2-4 *Nitzschia sigma* (Kützing) W. Smith (x1000)

5 *Cylindrotheca closterium* (Ehrenberg) Reimann & J.C. Lewin

6-7 *Cylindrotheca gracilis* (Brébisson ex Kützing) Grunow

8-10 *Tryblionella calida* (Grunow) D.G.Mann

11 *Tryblionella hungarica* (Grunow) Frenguelli

12-13 *Tryblionella apiculata* Gregory

14 *Tryblionella levidensis* W.Smith

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Plate 35

x2000

1 *Tryblionella circumscuta* (Bailey) Ralfs (x1000)

2-3 *Tryblionella gracilis* W. Smith

4-6 *Tryblionella navicularis* (Brébisson) Ralfs

Plate 36

x2000

- 1-3 *Amphora* cf. *copulata* (Kützing) Schoeman & Archibald (sensu Sabbe 1997)
- 4 *Amphora* cf. *helenensis* Giffen
- 5-7 *Amphora* cf. *indistincta* Levkov
- 8 *Amphora* aff. *pediculus* (Kützing) Grunow
- 9 *Amphora pediculus* (Kützing) Grunow
- 10-13 *Amphora* cf. *subacutiuscula* Schoeman
- 14 *Amphora ovalis* (Kützing) Kützing
- 15-17 *Amphora* cf. *vetula* Levkov
- 18 *Halamphora* sp. 1
- 19 *Halamphora* sp. 2
- 20-21 *Halamphora* cf. *abuensis* (Foged) Levkov
- 22 *Halamphora* sp. 3
- 23 *Eunotia* sp. 1
- 24 *Eunotia* cf. *minor* (Kützing) Grunow
- 25 *Catenula adhaerens* (Mereschkowsky) Mereschkowsky

Plate 37

x2000

1-3 *Entomoneis alata* (Ehrenberg) Ehrenberg

4 *Entomoneis paludosa* (W.Smith) Reimer

5 *Epithemia adnata* (Kützing) Brébisson

6 *Epithemia sorex* Kützing

Plate 38

x2000

1-2 *Surirella brebissonii* Krammer & Lange-Bertalot

3-4 *Surirella* sp. 4

5-7 *Surirella* sp. 1

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Plate 39

x2000

1-2 *Surirella* sp. 3

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Plate 40

x2000

- 1 *Surirella* cf. *turgida* W.Smith
- 2 *Petrodictyon gemma* (Ehrenberg) D.G.Mann (x1000)
- 3 *Surirella curvifacies* Brun
- 4-5 *Surirella atomus* Hustedt

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Plate 41

x2000

1 *Surirella* sp. 2

2 *Surirella fastuosa* (Ehrenberg) Ehrenberg (x1000)

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Plate 42

x2000

1-3 *Cymatopleura elliptica* (Brébisson) W.Smith

4 *Cymatopleura solea* (Brébisson) W.Smith (x1000)

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